

D2.2: Set of circularity indicators for Bio-based systems and guidance document for sustainability assessment of circular bio-based strategies

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

BbS – Bio-based systems
CEIP – Circular Economy Indicator Prototype
CMG – Circular material Guidelines
CMU – Circular Material Use rate
CPEI - Circular-process energy intensity
CPFI - Circular-Process Feedstock
CPI – Circular Performance Indicator
CPWF – Circular process waste factor
EF – Environmental Footprint
EI - Energy Intensity
ELCC – Environmental Life Cycle Costs
EoL – End of life
EVR – Eco-Cost Value ratio
DMC – Domestic material consumption
FI - Feedstock Intensity
GDP – Gross Domestic Product
LCA – Life cycle assessment
NCI – Nutrient circularity indicator
MCI – Material circularity index
MCPI - Material Circularity Performance Indicator
MFA – Material Flow Analysis
MFM – Material Flow Monitor
PR - Product Renewability
PtP – Package-to-product
RBR – Recyclability Benefit Rate
SEA – Statistical entropy analysis
SFA – Substance Flow Analysis
SLCA – Social Life Cycle Assessment
WF – Waste factor

PROJECT INFORMATION

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List of participants:

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5	NORGES TEKNISK-NATURVITENSKAPELIGE UNIVERSITET	NTNU
6	BIOECONOMY FOR CHANGE	B4C
7	BUSINESS E-INCUBATOR GO-UP	GOUP
8	FUNDACION CENTRO DE SERVICIOS Y PROMOCION FORESTAL Y DE SU INDUSTRIA DE CASTILLA Y LEON	CESEFOR
9	SONAE ARAUCO PORTUGAL SA	SONAE
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DELIVERABLE DETAILS

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Dissemination level	PU – Public, fully open
Period:	PR1
WP:	WP2 Improved methodologies for environmental sustainability and circularity assessment of Bio-based Systems (BbS)
Task:	T2.2 Improvement of Circularity assessment methodology for Bio-based systems
Author:	Anja Marie Bundgaard (AAU) & Mette Albert Mosgaard (AAU), Michael Saidani (LIST)
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Abstract:	<p>This deliverable reports on the results of Task 2.2 of the LCA4BIO project, which seeks to identify, map, analyse and select indicators for circularity in Bio-based Systems (BbS). Aiming to bridge the methodological gap in existing circular economy (CE) indicators, this work systematically identifies, evaluates, and consolidates indicators suitable for circular bio-based strategies across micro, meso, and macro levels. The methodology combines a systematic literature review with insights from key EU initiatives (CALIMERO, ORIENTING) and the newly established ISO 59000 series on CE. Evaluation criteria such as stakeholder acceptance, scientific robustness, and compatibility with life cycle assessment (LCA) principles were applied to derive three tailored indicator sets: a generic micro-level set, a macro-level set, and a sector-specific set for the wood industry. A total of 143 unique indicators were identified and mapped against key circularity strategies specific to BbS. The indicators address a wide range of CE strategies, including resource efficiency, waste valorisation, regeneration of natural systems, recirculation, cascading use, and social and economic viability. This work provides practical guidance for applying circularity assessments within sustainable bioeconomy frameworks. The outputs serve as a foundational tool for decision-makers, researchers, and practitioners engaged in evaluating and promoting circular bio-based solutions in Europe.</p>

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V1.0	16/06/2025	Draft for review
V2.0	30/06/2025	Final version
V3.0	31/10/2025	Revised version

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Context

This deliverable presents the results of Task 2.2, which focused on developing a structured and applicable indicator framework for assessing circularity in Bio-based Systems (BbS). The work involved a critical review of existing indicators from scientific literature, international standards (particularly the ISO 59000 series), and relevant EU projects (CALIMERO and ORIENTING). A total of 143 unique indicators were identified and mapped against key circularity strategies specific to BbS. Indicators were identified, categorized, and scored based on criteria such as applicability, transparency, and alignment with life cycle thinking. The outcome is a selection of circularity indicators mapped to key strategies relevant for BbS, covering both micro- and macro-level assessments, as well as a sector-specific set for the wood sector. These results form the basis of a guidance document that enables structured sustainability assessments of circular bio-based strategies.

1.2 Aim and objectives

The main objective of LCA4BIO task 2.2 is to develop a set of circularity indicators for BbS and a guidance document for sustainability assessment of circular bio-based strategies. This was done by:

- Identifying circular strategies that can be applied to BbS from the technical cycle and cascading;
- Identify macro and micro circularity indicators best fit for assessing the strategies based on a critical review of existing circular economy indicators in the scientific literature, the recently published 59000 series of standards on circular economy and the CALIMERO and Orienting EU projects;
- A categorisation, scoring and selection of indicators covering the two generic indicator sets for BbS covering the micro and macro level and an indicator set covering the wood sector which forms the basis for the sustainability assessment of circular bio-based strategies.

1.3 Circular bioeconomy

The circular bioeconomy, like the circular economy, is a concept with many definitions and interpretations. In Stegmann et al. (2020) a definition of a circular bioeconomy is proposed:

"The circular bioeconomy focuses on the sustainable, resource-efficient valorization of biomass in integrated, multi-output production chains (e.g. biorefineries) while also making use of residues and wastes and optimizing the value of biomass over time via cascading. Such an optimization can focus on economic, environmental or social aspects and ideally considers all three pillars of sustainability. The cascading steps aim at retaining the resource quality by adhering to the bio-based value pyramid and the waste hierarchy where possible and adequate." (Stegmann et al., 2020, p. 5)

This definition emphasizes several key aspects in understanding the circular bioeconomy, such as the importance of cascading and adhering to the bio-based value pyramid. Furthermore, it highlights the significance of the three pillars of sustainability: environmental, social, and economic.

There are also different conceptualizations of the interrelationship between the bioeconomy, circular economy, and the circular bio-based economy. The Ellen MacArthur Foundation views the circular bioeconomy as an integrated part of the circular economy, whereas other researchers consider the bioeconomy essential for achieving a circular economy, as all non-renewable resources must be replaced by renewable ones (Stegmann et al., 2020). Finally, some research sees the circular bioeconomy as the intersection between the circular economy and the bio-based sector (Stegmann et al., 2020).

1.4 Identification of strategies for a circular bioeconomy

In the project we are considering both circular strategies and circularity indicators therefore it is important to make a clear distinction between the two notions. In the study, a circular strategy is referred to as a systematic approach adopted by industries, organisations or governments on how to transition from a linear economic model to a circular economy model (Blomsma et al., 2019). Whereas, circularity indicators are metrics or indexes used to assess the degree to which a product, company, region or country aligns with the circularity strategy (Vogiantzi and Tserpes, 2023).

Strategies for a circular economy are commonly divided into the biological and technical cycles, as illustrated in the butterfly model developed by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation (2013). This distinction is important because circular economy strategies must be tailored to the specific system in which they are applied. The butterfly model highlights the importance of keeping biological materials within the biological cycle and technical materials within the technical cycle. However, this ideal separation is rarely achieved in practice. In reality, many products are composed of both biological and technical materials.

Figure 1: Butterfly model developed by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2013)

Over the years, several strategies or principles have emerged on how to create a circular economy. The Ellen MacArthur Foundation (2015) has developed the RESOLVE Framework, covering six business actions: (1) Regenerate – which covers a shift to renewable energy and materials. (2) Share – which implies that product loop speed should be low and the utilization of the products maximized by sharing them amongst users. (3) Optimize – which covers increased performance and efficiency of products. (4) Loop – which covers that products and materials should be kept in closed loops, and the inner loops should be prioritized (such as long lifespan, maintenance, and repair). (5) Virtualize – which covers the delivery of virtual utilities instead of, for instance, physical products. (6) Exchange – which covers the replacement of old materials with new, more advanced materials and the use of new technologies, products, and services.

Another very well-recognized framework is the R-strategies, which have developed from the 3Rs—reduce, reuse, and recycle—into the 9R strategies by Potting et al. (2017), covering, in addition to the 3Rs, also refuse, rethink, repair, refurbish, remanufacture, repurpose, and recover.

In the academic literature, the slow, narrow, close, regenerate, and inform models developed by Bocken et al. (2016) have also gained footing. The five strategies cover more specifically: Slowing: that resource loops are slowed through an increased lifetime of goods or an intensified use of the goods or products. Closing: that the

resource loops are closed through recycling. Narrowing: that resources are used efficiently. Regenerate: that products are clean, hence free of toxic substances, and to increase the use of renewable materials and energy. Inform: which covers the use of information technologies to support a circular economy.

What all these strategies and models have in common is a distinct focus on circularity strategies relevant for the technical system, whereas strategies such as cascading and biorefining from the biological system are less considered.

However, in recent years, studies have also focused on the biological system and the circularity strategies relevant here. In Vural et al. (2022), six circular economy principles for biobased products are defined, taking into consideration the characteristics of biobased products (Table 1). Furthermore, the article defines nine aspects that need to be measured when monitoring the circularity of biobased products.

Circular economy Principles	What to measure?
1. Reduce reliance on fossil resources	1. Share of renewable resources
2. Use resources efficiently	2. Resource use efficiency (including use of residues)
3. Valorise waste and residues	3. Degree of regeneration
4. Regenerate	4. Degree of recirculation
5. Recirculate	5. Utility (including cascading use)
6. Extend the high-quality use of biomass	6. Risk of accumulation of hazardous substances
	7. Effect on environmental protection
	8. Effect on economic viability
	9. Effect on social equity

Table 1: Overview of circular economy principles and what needs to be measured from Vural et al. (2022)

1.4.1 The circular strategies developed in the study for biobased systems

The circular strategies developed in the study for biobased systems

As part of this study, a tailored framework of circular strategies for bio-based systems was developed. This framework integrates strategies from both the biological and technical cycles, including cascading use and R-strategies. It builds upon the comprehensive review of circular economy (CE) principles and strategies by Vural et al. (2022), and incorporates their subsequent refinement of the framework presented in Vural et al. (2023). To ensure relevance to the study context, the framework was further adapted and expanded to include strategies from the technical cycle, particularly those related to R-strategies.

As discussed in Section 1.3.1, the R-strategies have played a central role in conceptualizing circular economy approaches, especially within the technical cycle. Initially introduced as the 3Rs, Reduce, Reuse, Recycle, the concept has evolved significantly over time. The European Waste Framework Directive expanded this to 4Rs by adding Recovery. Later, Potting et al. proposed a more comprehensive R10 framework, which includes additional strategies such as Refuse, Rethink, Repair, Refurbish, Remanufacture, and Repurpose (see Table X for an overview). Recent literature has further broadened the scope of R-strategies. Reike et al. (2018) identified up to 38 RE-strategies, while Zorpas (2024) reported over 100 R-strategies in the circular economy literature. These strategies are typically organized in a hierarchical order, emphasizing the prioritization of actions that preserve product value. For example, refusing a product is preferred over Repairing, and Refurbishment should precede Recycling.

Strategies	R-Strategies	Description
Use resources efficiently including residues and wastes	R0-Refuse	Make the product redundant
	R1-Rethink	Make product use more intensive
	R2-Reduce	Increase efficiency in product production and consumption reduce use of natural resources and materials
Recirculate	R3-Reuse	Use the product again with its original function
	R4-Repair	Make defective products usable again for the original function though repair and maintenance
	R5-Refurbish	Restore an old product and bring it up to date
	R6- Remanufacture	Use defective products or parts of defective products in a new product with the same function
	R7-Repurpose	Use defective products or parts of defective products in a new product with a new function
	R8-Recycle	Extract the materials to obtain the same or lower quality material
Reduce reliance on fossil resources and increase share of renewable resources	R9-Recover	Energy recovery

Table 2: Overview of the covered R-strategies adopted by Potting et al. (2017)

As mentioned, the circularity strategies and the aspects to be measured developed by Vural Gursel et al. (2022) and (2023) have formed the basis for understanding the project’s framework of circular strategies and sub-strategies for bio-based systems, as well as for the subsequent categorization of identified indicators. However, these strategies have been adapted to fit the project context, and Principle 7 was excluded, as it is already covered by the project’s LCA methodology. Furthermore, the 10R strategies were added as sub-strategies under the main CE strategies: *use resources efficiently (including residues)*, *recirculate* and *reduce reliance on fossil resources, and increase the share of renewable resources* (see Table 2). The 10R strategies were selected because they represent one of the most comprehensive frameworks while remaining operational. The strategies and sub-strategies applied in the project are introduced in Table 3.

Circularity strategies	Sub-strategies	Description
Reduce reliance on fossil resources and increase share of renewable	Energy efficiency	The transition from fossil resources to renewable resources such as biomass and renewable energy.
	Recover	
	Use of renewable resources, including energy	

resources		
Use resources efficiently, including residues and wastes	Reduce/ Resource efficiency Rethink Refuse Waste monitoring and reduction	More efficient use of resources and utilise residues and wastes
Regenerate	Generic indicators targeting regeneration Sustainable sourcing Maintaining carbon cycles Maintaining nutrient cycles	The process to restore and regenerate ecosystems. The ecosystem should remain healthy and therefore it is essential to maintain soil carbon and nutrient cycles, avoid hazardous substances and ensure sustainable sourcing
Recirculate	Reuse Repair Refurbish Remanufacture Recycle Maximisation of use (durability)	Covers chemical and mechanical recycling and various R-strategies to extend the use phase of a product or its components.
Extend the high-quality use of biomass (including cascading use)	Bio-based value pyramid Cascading Composting	To optimize the time the product, material, and substance spend in the cycle and ensure consecutive cycles while minimizing quality losses.
Positive effect on economic viability		The economic aspects of circularity
Positive effect on social viability		The social aspects of circularity
Complex indicators		Indicators covering more than one strategy

Table 3: Overview of the circularity strategies and sub-strategies applied in the project

1.5 Existing reviews of CE indicators for biobased systems

Several reviews already exist of indicators for biobased systems. The following section will provide a short account of their main findings.

Poponi et al. (2022) create a dashboard of indicators to be used for the agri-food sector to assess progress towards a circular economy. A total of 102 indicators were obtained, covering aspects such as air, water, soil, energy, waste, cost, value and productivity, knowledge, equality, and innovation at the macro, meso, and micro levels. The article by Mesa et al. (2024) assesses existing CBE indicators. Thirteen CBE indicators were identified through a literature review (biomass utilization efficiency, biomass utilisation factor, bioresource utilization index, cascade factor, biogenic carbon storage, 3R set of indicators, material circularity index, techno-economic sustainability analysis, hybridized sustainability indicators, and integrated assessment tool). The

indicators were then categorized based on purpose and definition. The study urges the development of a combined set of indicators covering specific industries or cases, instead of focusing on a new single indicator that strives to cover all aspects.

Aragonés et al. (2024) make a review of available approaches for evaluating circularity, covering both the biological and the technical cycle. 105 references are covered in the article, and they have been categorized according to the level they cover (macro, meso, micro, and nano), the cycle (biological, technical, or both), the method used, and the sector covered. The review is used to create a decision support tool that can be used by stakeholders to select the most suitable approach depending on the information needed. Kooduvalli et al. (2019) provide a systematic review of sustainability indicators for biobased product manufacturing. The article provides 33 core indicators covering 22 different categories, which can be used to assess the sustainability of manufacturing biobased products across the three disciplines: manufacturing, biomass, and materials. The indicators relevant across the three disciplines examined (manufacturing, biomass, and materials) are air quality, GHG, water quality and quantity, energy consumption, profitability, biodiversity, culture, equity, and health and safety. Navare et al. (2021) review circular economy monitoring criteria and circular economy assessment tools to assess whether they cover the four characteristics of the biological system. These four characteristics are: sustainable harvesting of biotic resources, cascading, the safe return of nutrients to support regeneration, and environmental impacts due to resource extraction, land use, resource depletion, and biogenic carbon flows. The study concludes that the existing circular economy monitoring framework falls short of covering the characteristics of the biological system. However, the study further concludes that new assessments do not have to be developed, but existing indicators and assessment frameworks can fill the gap. The study by Vural et al. (2023) provides a systematic review of circularity indicators at the micro level. It provides an analysis of 25 indicators on how well they cover the circular economy aspects that need to be measured, as proposed in Vural et al. (2022) and as presented in Table 2.

The present study is inspired by the approach taken in Vural et al. (2023) but additionally extends the scope to also cover the meso and macro levels. Furthermore, the present study focuses more on simple indicators targeting the individual circularity strategies relevant for BbS, instead of indicators covering all aspects, and on sector-specific indicator sets in line with the conclusions provided by Mesa et al. (2024).

2 METHODS

The research design was structured as a critical review of circularity indicators used for BbS in the scientific literature (Figure 2). This was supplemented with indicators from the ISO 59000 series of standards and two selected EU projects also focused on the circularity assessment of BbS: the ORIENTING and CALIMERO projects. These sources form the basis for a database of circularity indicators and tools. Based on 12 evaluation criteria, a scoring of the identified indicators was conducted, covering aspects such as stakeholder acceptance, applicability, transparency, scientific robustness, completeness, and compatibility. Based on the scoring—supplemented with results from the ORIENTING and CALIMERO projects and the ISO 59020—indicators were selected for three indicator sets: a generic indicator set at the micro level, a generic indicator set at the macro level, and an indicator set targeting the wood sector at the meso and macro levels. These indicator sets form the basis of the guidance document for sustainability assessment of circular bio-based strategies, in combination with a procedure for how to perform the assessment.

Figure 2: Overview of the research design and project flow

2.1 Review of literature on circularity indicators for BbS

The identification of relevant circularity indicators for BbS was based on a systematic review of scientific literature following the PRISMA approach (Page et al., 2021). Scopus was selected as the primary database for the literature review as it is one of the most comprehensive databases, especially covering natural sciences, medicine, and technology, as well as social sciences and humanities. A study by Aksnes et al. (2019) on the Scopus coverage of Norwegian scientific and scholarly publications showed that Scopus covers 85% of the publications within natural sciences and technology for the years 2015 and 2016. A specific search was carried out using the terms: circular OR “circular AND economy” OR circularity AND bio* AND indicator* OR index OR metric in titles, abstracts, or keywords. Only English references were included, and reviews and conference reviews were excluded from the search. The specific search string is provided in Table 4.

Search string

```
( TITLE-ABS-
KEY ( circular OR circular AND economy OR circularity AND bio OR biological AND indicator* O
R Index OR metric ) AND LANGUAGE ( english ) ) AND
NOT DOCTYPE ( re ) AND ( EXCLUDE ( DOCTYPE , "cr" ) )
```

Table 4: Overview of the search strategy

The identification, screening, and inclusion process of the review is illustrated in Figure 2. Initially, 292 records were identified before excluding non-English records and review papers. Applying these exclusion criteria resulted in the exclusion of 45 records, leaving 246 records for screening. Based on the screening of titles and abstracts, 194 records were deemed irrelevant and excluded. Here, records were excluded which did not focus on circularity indicators, indexes or metrics. Consequently, 53 reports were sought for retrieval, and all were successfully retrieved. After reading and assessing the eligibility of these reports, 17 were excluded for the following reasons: 6 focused on broader sustainability indicators without specific reference to circularity, 3 did not relate to BbS, 7 did not provide any relevant indications, and 1 was a review despite the specific exclusion of reviews. This process resulted in the inclusion of 36 reports from the Scopus database. The reports from Scopus were analysed in a review matrix covering the following themes: publication year, product group, region, method, level, status of the indicator (developed, selected or applied), main conclusions and the identified circularity indicators on micro, meso and macro level. The identified circularity indicators were then categorized according to the circularity strategies elaborated in Table 3.

Stage	Exclusion criteria	Inclusion criteria
Before screening	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reviews Non-English records 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Should be original contributions not reviews Only English records
Screening	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Records which did not deal with circularity indicators, indexes or metrics plus biobased systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The records should deal with circularity indicators, indexes or metrics
Assessed for eligibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Focused on broader sustainability indicators without specific reference to circularity Did not relate to BbS Did not provide any relevant indications Was a review despite the specific exclusion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Records focus on circularity indicators, indexes or metrics Records related to BbS Should provide provide relevant circularity indicators, indexes or metrics

Table 5: Overview of exclusion and inclusion criteria

Additionally, three other relevant sources were included in the review: the CALIMRO deliverables 1.3 and 3.2, the ORIENTING deliverable 1.4 on a critical evaluation of material criticality and product-related circularity approaches, and the ISO 59000 series of standards on circularity. The CALIMRO and ORIENTING deliverables were included as coordination with these projects is part of the task 2.2 description. The ISO 59000 series of standards was included as they are expected to initiate the standardization of circularity concepts and indicators. These were used to validate the indicators identified in the systematic literature review of the scientific literature.

Figure 3: Overview of the search strategy (PRISMA)

2.2 Selection of circularity indicators

After identifying and categorizing the indicators, they were selected based on several criteria. These criteria were adapted from the ORIENTING project but simplified and tailored to the purpose of this deliverable. The development of the criteria was an iterative process involving product partners in task 2.2, including LCA and circularity experts. The criteria are detailed in Table 6 and Appendix 2 and 3. Emphasis was placed on applicability/complexity and a life-cycle approach, with three specific criteria highlighted due to the intended application of the indicator framework in connection with LCA and as part of a simplified circularity tool in WP6.

Criteria	Detailed criteria
1. Stakeholder acceptance	1.1 Acceptance by academia – used in academic studies 1.2 Acceptance in practice
2. Applicability/ complexity	2.1 The indicator has low complexity 2.2 Data is easily availability (both primary and secondary) 2.3 The tool linked to the indicator is freely available
3. Transparency	3.1 Transparency of the modelling data and the model used
4. Scientific robustness	4.1 The indicator is peer-reviewed
5. Completeness	5.1 The indicator covers the key aspects of the CE strategy 5.2 The indicator covers more than one CE strategy
6. Compatibility with life-cycle approach	6.1 Follows a life cycle approach 6.2 Can be calculated using LCI data 6.3 Is already used in combination with LCA

Table 6: Overview of the selection criteria for the circularity indicators

The process of evaluating the circularity indicators according to the selection criteria involved several steps. First, one of the project partners graded the circularity indicators. Next, the remaining project partners involved in the task reviewed these gradings. Then, any disagreements regarding the gradings were discussed and resolved during a meeting. Finally, the scores were categorized into five groups, ranging from very poor, poor, neutral, good, to very good (see Table 7).

-12 to -8	Very poor
-7 to -3	Poor
-2 to 2	Neutral
3 to 7	Good
8 to 12	Very good

Table 7: Categorization according to the scoring

3 RESULTS OF THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

The following chapter presents the results of the scientific literature review. It begins with a summary of the main findings, followed by a detailed presentation of the identified indicators. These indicators are organized according to the specific circularity strategies they address.

3.1 Main results of the literature review

The following section provides an analysis of the results from the scientific literature review, focusing on key aspects such as the diversity of applied indicators, the extent to which different circularity strategies are covered, and the sectoral distribution of the studies.

3.1.1 Diversity in the applied indicators

The review of the literature revealed a high degree of diversity in the circularity indicators used to assess the circularity of BbS. A total of 143 distinct circularity indicators were identified across 39 review papers. Notably, 136 of these indicators were used only once in the reviewed literature (see Table 8), highlighting the fragmented nature of current assessment practices.

This finding supports previous research Poponi et al. (2022) suggesting that there is no standardized or unified set of indicators for evaluating the circularity of BbS. Instead, a wide array of indicators is employed, reflecting a pluralistic approach to assessment. Only a few indicators were used more than once: four indicators appeared in two studies, one in three studies, one in five studies, and one in eight studies.

It is important to note that this overview does not account for the reuse of the same indicators across different analytical levels (micro, meso, and macro). For instance, both Material Flow Analysis (MFA) and resource productivity were used twice at the macro level and once at the meso level.

	Micro	Meso	Macro	Total
Indicator used in one study	38	56	42	136
Indicators used in two studies	1	0	3	4
Indicator used in three studies	1	0	0	1
Indicator used in five studies	1	0	0	1
Indicators used in eight studies	1	0	0	1

Table 8: Overview of the number of indicators used in one, two, five or eight studies. This does not cover the same indicators used across studies.

Indicators and methods used in more than one study are listed in Table 9. The most frequently applied circularity indicator was the Material Circularity Indicator (MCI), which appeared in eight studies. Of these, the updated 2019 version—adopted bio-based systems—was used in three studies, while the original 2015 version was applied with various adaptations in five studies.

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) emerged as the most commonly used method for assessing circularity aspects, often in combination with specific circularity indicators, as discussed in section 3.11.

Recycling rates were used in two studies: Horvath et al. (2019) and Poponi et al. (2024). However, their approaches differ Horvath et al. excluded major mineral waste, whereas Poponi et al. included all waste types. Additionally, recycling rates were applied in three other studies focusing on specific waste fractions, including packaging waste, biowaste, and municipal waste, as reported by Vuta et al. (2018).

Material Flow Analysis (MFA) and resource productivity indicators were used in two macro-level studies and one meso-level study, totaling three applications across different analytical levels.

Finally, the Environmental Life Cycle Costing (ELCC) method was used in two studies at the micro level.

Some conceptual similarities were observed between the nutrient circularity indicators developed by Poponi et al. (2024) and Pérez-Mercado et al. (2022), as both focus on nutrient recirculation in waste. However, their scopes differ: Poponi et al. concentrate specifically on food waste, while Pérez-Mercado et al. address all waste types at the national level.

Indicator	Used in number of studies (micro)	Used in number of studies (meso)	Used in number of studies (macro)	Used in number of studies across levels (total)
Recycling rates	0	0	2 (+3)	2 (+3)
Material flow analysis	0	1	2	3
Resource productivity indicator	0	1	2	3
ELCC	2	0	0	2
MCI from 2019	3	0	0	3
MCI original but with adaptations	5	0	0	5
LCA	8	0	0	8

Table 9: Indicators used in more than one study

3.1.2 Coverage of the different CE strategies

The review also revealed variation in the number of circularity indicators associated with the identified circularity strategies (see Table 10). This suggests differing levels of maturity among the indicators used to assess various strategies. These differences were also influenced by the analytical level considered—micro, meso, or macro.

Strategy	Number of indicators identified (micro)	Number of indicators identified (meso)	Number of indicators identified (macro)	Number of indicators (total)
Reduce reliance on fossil fuels	5	3	5	13
Use resource efficiently, including residues and wastes	12	3	14	29
Regenerate	2	11	12	25
Recirculate	8	0	7	16
Maximize the utility of products (including cascading use)	1	(7)	1	2/(9)
Positive effect on economic viability	3	2	2	7
Positive effect on social equality	1	(27)	1	2/(29)

Complex indicators

10

1

3

14

Table 10: Coverage of the different CE strategies

At the micro level, the highest number of indicators were identified for the strategies use resources efficiently (including residues and waste), recirculate, and complex indicators. In contrast, the fewest indicators were found for the strategies regenerate, maximize the utility of products (including cascading use), and positive effect on social equality, suggesting a lower maturity level for developing indicators targeting these areas.

At the meso level, most indicators were associated with the strategy positive effect on social equality. However, this was largely due to a single study by Costa et al. (2023), which proposed a comprehensive set of indicators to assess the circularity of Alpine collective ownerships. Similarly, seven indicators targeting maximize the utility of products (including cascading use) also originated from this study. These indicators are highly specific to collective ownership contexts and may be less applicable in other settings.

For the strategy regenerate, eleven indicators were identified at the meso level. These covered a range of aspects, including general regenerative principles, carbon cycle maintenance, and sustainable sourcing and yield. This suggests that regenerate is more commonly assessed at the meso level rather than at the company or product (micro) level.

At the macro level, most indicators were found for the strategies use resources efficiently (including residues and waste) (14 indicators) and regenerate (12 indicators), followed by recirculate (7 indicators) and reduce reliance on fossil fuels (5 indicators). Many of these indicators were based on Eurostat data, such as waste generation, recycling rates, and land use. The fewest indicators were identified for maximize the utility of products (including cascading use) (1 indicator), positive effect on social equality (1 indicator), and positive effect on economic viability (2 indicators).

When excluding the Costa et al. (2023) study, it becomes evident that indicators for maximize the utility of products (including cascading use) and positive effect on social equality are the least developed across all analytical levels. This highlights a clear need for further research to develop robust indicators for these strategies at the micro, meso, and macro levels.

In the case of maximize the utility of products (including cascading use), the challenge extends beyond indicator development. It also requires appropriate modeling of multifunctionality in line with the bio-based value pyramid, as illustrated in Figure 4.

Overall, the indicator landscape appears more mature for the strategies use resources efficiently (including residues and waste), regenerate, and recirculate, as these had the highest number of indicators. Moving forward, efforts should focus on standardizing and aligning these indicators to promote consistency and comparability across studies.

3.1.3 Sector coverage

The reviewed articles covered a wide range of sectors, as illustrated in Figure 4. The most represented sectors were agriculture and food products, featured in eight articles, followed by plastic products—including bioplastics—with seven articles. Six articles had a broader, more generic focus on bio-based systems.

Three articles focused specifically on circularity assessments at the country level, nutrient management, and forest and wood-based products, respectively. Additionally, two studies addressed construction products, particularly asphalt. One article each focused on textiles, wastewater, and soil.

No studies were found on biochemicals, which represents a limitation of this review. Despite the sector-specific focus of many articles, several of the identified indicators were generic in nature and could be applied across different sectors beyond the case studies presented. An exception was found in the articles focused on the forest and wood sector, where many indicators were highly sector-specific. Due to this specificity, a separate

set of wood-based indicators was developed and evaluated independently.

Figure 4: Overview of the sector coverage of the selected articles

3.2 Indicators targeting - Reduce reliance on fossil resources

One of the main categories of indicators that were identified in the review relates to reducing the reliance on fossil fuels, it mainly relates to industrial processes (Table 12). The indicators focus on various aspects such as energy efficiency, renewable energy adoption, and energy sufficiency. The indicators are applied for different sectors, and this is specified below as they are presented.

The article by Lokesh et al. (2020) covers several circularity indicators, targeting the strategy to reduce reliance on fossil resources, the Product Renewability (PR) indicator, the Energy Intensity (EI) indicator, and the circular-process energy intensity (CPEI). The CPEI can be used for circular processes to validate waste valorization and material circulation strategies.

The PR indicator is intended to substantiate bio-based claims of products, and focus on the materials used in the processes. The PR indicator is calculated using the following formula:

$$PR = \left[\frac{M_{Bio_feed} + M_{Bio_Comp_inp}}{M_{Net_feed} + M_{net_Comp_inp}} \cdot 100 \right] \quad (1)$$

Where:

- M_{Bio_feed} is the net mass of bio-derived primary feedstock incorporated into the product (kg)
- $M_{Bio_Comp_inp}$ is the net mass of bio-derived substances incorporated into the final formulation (compositional input) (kg)
- M_{Net_feed} is the net mass of all primary feedstocks incorporated into the product (kg)
- $M_{net_comp_inp}$ is the net mass of all the materials incorporated into the final formulation (compositional inputs) (kg)

The EI indicator supplements the above by addressing the energy used for industrial processes.

The EI indicator is calculated using the following formula:

$$EI = \frac{E_{FosD} + E_{RenD} - E_{IntD}}{M_{Prod} + M_{Co.prod}} \quad (2)$$

The CEPI indicator supplements the two indicators above by adding a circularity focus, where co-products and recovered and recycled products and energy are included. The CPEI is calculated using the following formula:

$$CPEI = \frac{E_{FosD} + E_{RenD} - E_{IntD}}{M_{Prod} + M_{Co.prod} + M_{re.prod}} \quad (3)$$

Where:

- E_{FosD} is the fossil-derived energy use (kW h)
- E_{RenD} is the renewable energy used (kW h)
- E_{IntD} is the internally derived energy used (kW h)
- M_{Prod} is the total mass of the product (kg)
- $M_{Co.prod}$ is the total mass of the co-product (kg)
- $M_{re.prod}$ is the total mass of the recovered and recycled product

Another approach is taken in the article by Hildebrandt et al. (2017) that provides a classification system to assess the recyclability performance of bio-based polymers. The system includes three quantitative indicators targeting energy and the use of fossil-based additives:

- the cumulated energy demand ($CE_{polym.recov.}$),
- the energy yields ($y_{energy recyc}$) and
- the net calorific value and the non-substitutable elements of fossil-based additives that need to be subtracted

The article by Poponi et al. (2024) provides several indicators to assess the circularity of waste management from organic farms. Three of these targets energy and covers recovery of energy by using waste (EE_p), energy required (EE_r) and the energy self-sufficiency indicator (ESS_{EE}). EE_p is expressed in GW/year and is calculated by using the following equation:

$$EE_p = w \cdot Q \cdot CP_{ee} \quad (4)$$

The energy self-sufficiency indicator (ESS_{EE}) is calculated using the following equation:

$$ESS_{EE} = \frac{EE_p}{EE_r} \quad (5)$$

Where according to Sgarbossa and Russo (2017):

- Q is the processed animal per year
- w is tonnes of animal fat per processed animal or tonnes of organic waste per processed animal
- CP_{EE} is the treated waste converted into electric energy and thermal energy
- EE_r is the energy needed by the production process where the waste is created

The study by Pieratti et al. (2019) defines a set of circularity indicators for assessing forest-wood chains following the 4Rs (reduce, reuse, recycled and recover). The indicators are tested on a forest area in the Tuscany region. The study provides two indicators for energy recovery at end-of-life (I_5 and I_6). Where I_5 is the ratio between the CO₂ emissions prevented by selling the timber for energy products (with respect to diesel oil) and the total cubic meter collected. I_6 is the ratio between deadwood used for energy purposes and the total deadwood in the forest.

Indicators	Description	Level	Reference
Product renewability (PR)	The ratio between bio-derived feedstock and substances and the total feedstock and all materials incorporated into the final product	Micro	(Lokesh et al., 2020)
Energy intensity (EI)	The ratio between the total amount of energy and the total amount of products and co-products produced	Micro	(Lokesh et al., 2020)
Circular-Process Energy Intensity (CPEI)	The ratio between the total amount of energy and the total amount product, co-product, recovered product and recycled product	Micro	(Lokesh et al., 2020)
Cumulative energy demand (CED)	The value is provided in kWh kg ⁻¹ and covers the cumulated energy demand for the waste treatment and material recovery process for the recycled polymer	Micro	(Hildebrandt et al., 2017)
Rate of energy recovery	The energy yields for energetic recycling of the fraction at end-of-life	Micro	(Hildebrandt et al., 2017)
The net calorific value and non- substitutable elements	This covers the elements that still need to be derived from fossil-based sources.	Micro	(Hildebrandt et al., 2017)
Fossil fuel consumption by use	No further information is provided	Meso	(Li et al., 2021)
Volume of thinned timber and amount that can be used as woody biomass	Thinning should help produce high-quality timber while maintaining biodiversity	Meso	(Li et al., 2021)
Electricity/ thermal efficiency of woody biomass and creation of economic value	No further information is provided	Meso	(Li et al., 2021)
Recovery of energy using waste	The energy generated by waste recovery	Macro	(Poponi et al., 2024)
Energy required	The energy needed by the production process where the waste is produced	Macro	(Poponi et al., 2024)
Energy self-sufficiency	Express the degree of energy self-sufficiency as a function of waste recovery and the energy generated	Macro	(Poponi et al., 2024)
I ₅	Ration between the CO ₂ emissions saved by the timber sold for energy production and the total cubic meter collected (kg CO ₂ M ⁻³)	Macro	(Pieratti et al., 2019)

I ₆	Ration between deadwood used for energy production and total deadwood (m ³ m ⁻³)	Macro	(Pieratti et al., 2019)
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Table 12: Overview of the energy-related indicators identified in the review

3.3 Indicators targeting - Use resources efficiently including use of residues and wastes

Another central strategy in a circular economy is the efficient use of resources. The review identified several indicators targeting resource efficiency (Table 13). Additionally, the use of residues and waste is another important aspect, with several indicators identified targeting waste management (Table 14).

3.3.1 Use resources efficiently

The article by Lokesh et al. (2020) introduces Feedstock Intensity (FI) and Circular-Process Feedstock Intensity (CPFI). FI is defined as the ratio of the total amount of raw materials used to the total amount of useful output, covering both end-products and co-products. It is intended for linear processes. FI is measured in kilograms of feedstock and can be calculated using the following formula:

$$FI = \frac{M_{raw.mat}}{M_{main.prod} + M_{co.prod}} \quad (6)$$

Where:

- $M_{raw.mat}$ is the total mass of primary feedstock going into the process (kg)
- $M_{main.prod}$ is the total mass of the target product because of the process in kg
- $M_{co.prod}$ is the total mass of any useful co-product resulting from the process in kg

For circular processes, the CPFI should be used. It is also measured in kg and can be calculated using the following formula:

$$CPFI = \frac{M_{raw.mat}}{M_{main.prod} + M_{co.prod} + M_{re.mat}} \quad (7)$$

Where:

- $M_{re.mat}$ is the total mass of the material recovered/ recycled from product waste or EoL in kg

The article by Hildebrandt et al. (2017) examines the design for recycling of bio-based polymers and possible constraints in the recycling infrastructure. It provides recommendations on how the use of life cycle assessment indicators can promote design for recycling principles and improve the cascading use of bio-based polymers. Although the article targets cascading use indicators, the selected indicators cover different circular economy strategies. One of these indicators is the efficiency of material use, which is defined as the product recovered per kilogram of raw material input for single material life cycles and gathered along a series of life cycles.

The article by Molina-Sánchez et al. (2018) provides a set of sustainability indicators for wastewater management within a circular economy model for the paper industry. It introduces a set of circular economy indicators, two of which target the efficient use of resources: the reductive indicator of circular economy efficiency for water ($I_{WCE,r}$) and the productive indicator of circular economy efficiency for water ($I_{WCE,p}$). The reductive indicator of circular economy efficiency for water is calculated using the following formula:

$$I_{W,CE,r} = \frac{Q_{EF}}{Q_{W,T}} \cdot 100 \quad (8)$$

Where:

- Q_{EF} is the volumetric flow of the treated water, which can be recovered as a result of the treatment process.
- $Q_{W,T}$ is the total volumetric water flow consumed in the paper production

The productive indicator of circular economy efficiency for water is calculated using the following formula:

$$I_{W,CE,p} = I_{W,TN} \cdot \frac{Q_{PMW}}{P_p} \quad (9)$$

Where,

- Q_{PMW} is the volumetric flow of wastewater from the paper mill
- P_p is the mass flow of paper produced
- $I_{W,TN}$ is the technological nutrient performance for water

The technological nutrient performance for water is calculated using the following formula:

$$I_{W,TN} = \frac{Q_{EF}}{Q_{PMW}} \quad (10)$$

The article by Stanchev et al. (2020) proposes a measuring framework to assess the environmental performance of circular solutions for anaerobic treatment of dairy processing effluents. It introduces the Material Circularity Performance Indicator (MCPI), which assesses the extent to which the baseline demand for energy and resource flow is minimized to actually close resource and energy demands. It is calculated using the following formula:

$$MCPI = \frac{\text{Baseline demand} - \text{minimised demand}}{\text{Baseline demand}} \quad (11)$$

The results will range from 0 to 1, where 1 means that the demand is completely covered and 0 means that there are no reductions in demand.

The article by Hildebrandt et al. (2017) introduces the substitution factor of virgin materials in (kg/kg), defined as the amount of virgin material substituted per kilogram of input of secondary raw material for each stage where secondary raw materials are recovered.

The article by Molona-Sánchez et al. (2018) provides a set of sustainability indicators for wastewater management in the paper industry focused on circular solutions. Two indicators target the efficient use of resources, measuring the relative amount of water and sludge that can be recovered relative to the total flows. The indicators are the Technological Nutrient Performance for Water ($I_{W,TN}$) and the Technological Nutrient Performance for the recovered sludge ($I_{SG,TN}$). The Technological Nutrient Performance for Water is calculated using the following formula:

$$I_{W,TN} = \frac{Q_{EF}}{Q_{PMW}} \quad (12)$$

Where:

- Q_{EF} is the volumetric flow of treated water that can be recovered as a result of the treatment process.
- Q_{PMW} is the volumetric flow of wastewater from the process.

The Technological Nutrient Performance for the recovered sludge ($I_{SG,TN}$) is calculated using the following formula:

$$I_{SG,TN} = \frac{m_{SG,R}}{Q_{PMW}} \quad (13)$$

Where:

- $M_{SG,R}$ is the mass flow of recovered sludge as a result of the waste treatment process.

The article by Gao et al. (2020) used material flow analysis (MFA) to assess the circularity of a region. Additionally, it is supplemented by intensity efficiency indexes of MFA based on resource consumption per capita and per 100,000 RMB of GDP.

The article by Kusumo et al. (2022) introduces resource productivity indicators based on Wen and Meng (2015). Wen and Meng (2015) combine the resource productivity indicator (RP) with substance flow analysis (SFA) to evaluate industrial symbiosis solutions, focusing on the circuit board industry and targeting copper, water, and energy.

The study by Horvalth et al. (2019) develops a set of indicators to measure circular efficiency based on the existing ecological capacity of the country. This includes two indicators targeting efficient use of resources: domestic material consumption and resource productivity.

The article by Vuta et al. (2018) estimates the impact that circularity measures can have on resource productivity and economic growth. Here, the resource productivity indicator is calculated as the ratio of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) to domestic material consumption, based on the EUROSTAT database.

The study by Poponi et al. (2024) provides circularity indicators for waste management in bio-districts. One of the indicators targets efficient use of packaging material by introducing the package-to-product (PtP) indicator. Specifically, the indicator was used to assess the environmental impact of food packaging. The indicator is calculated using the following formula:

$$P_t P_{cc}(\%) = \frac{\sum CC_{Pa}}{\sum CC_{Pr}} \cdot 100 \quad (14)$$

Where:

- CC_{Pa} is the climate impact caused by the packaging material
- CC_{Pr} is the climate impact caused by the product

The article by Pieratti et al. (2019) introduces two indicators targeted at the efficient use of resources. The first indicator is the ratio between the economic value of harvested wood in cubic meters and the forest area on an annual basis (I₁). The indicator is calculated using the following formula:

$$I_1 = \frac{\text{annual economic value}}{\text{cubic meter of wood harvested}} \left[\frac{\text{€}}{\text{m}^3} \right] \quad (15)$$

The second indicators I₂ is the CO₂ emissions of the phase of the forest-wood chain (covering the felling to the transport) for unit volume in (kgCO₂m⁻³). It is calculated using the following formula:

$$I_2 = \frac{\text{CO}_2 \text{ emissions in the forest-wood chain}}{\text{Wood volume harvest}} \left[\frac{\text{kgCO}_2}{\text{m}^3} \right] \quad (16)$$

The article by Kusumo et al. (2022) mentions the use of material flow analysis (MFA) as a circular economy (CE) indicator for biological cycles on a macro level. MFA is typically defined as “a systematic assessment of the flow and stocks of materials within a system defined in space and time” (Brunner and Rechberger, 2017), and thus MFA is a method rather than a specific indicator. Kusumo et al. (2022) refers to a study by Haupt et al. (2017) where a material flow analysis is performed on the Swiss waste management system to assess the resource efficiency of the system. More specifically, recycling rates are used as an indicator to assess the circularity of the system.

The article by Laner et al. (2017) uses statistical entropy analysis (SEA) to evaluate resource efficiency in a case study of phosphorus use. SEA is a variant of material flow analysis (MFA) where the concentrations of a resource in a material flow are used as a proxy for resource quality. Thus, SEA becomes a method to evaluate a material flow system in terms of its ability to dilute or concentrate resources throughout its life cycle.

The article by Delahaye et al. (2023) develops a Material Flow Monitor (MFM) database to monitor Dutch circular economy efforts. The MFM is a physical supply and use table built on national economic and

environmental accounting statistics. The MFM can then be used as the basis to calculate a number of circularity indicators, such as resource efficiency, dependency, and substitution.

Indicators	Description	Level	Reference
Feedstock intensity (FI)	The ratio of the total amount of the main raw materials used to the total amount of useful output including both end-products and co-products	Micro	(Lokesh et al., 2020)
Circular-process feedstock intensity (CPFI)	The ratio of the total amount of the main raw material used to the total amount of useful output for both end-products and co-products and the total mass of the materials recovered or recycled	Micro	(Lokesh et al., 2020)
Rate of material use efficiency	Kg of product recovered per kg of raw material input for individual material life cycles and gathered along a series of life cycles	Micro	(Hildebrandt et al., 2017)
Reductive indicator of circular economy efficiency for water	Covers the reduction in water used in the paper manufacturing process.	Micro	(Molina-Sánchez et al., 2018)
Productive indicator of circular economy efficiency for water	Covers the volumetric flow of treated water which is recovered relative to the mass flow of paper produced	Micro	(Molina-Sánchez et al., 2018)
Material circularity performance (MCPI)	Assesses to which extent a minimized demand closes the baseline resource or energy demand	Micro	(Stanchev et al., 2020)
The substitution factor of virgin materials	Virgin material substituted per kg of input of secondary raw material	Micro	(Hildebrandt et al., 2017)
Technological nutrient performance for the recovered sludge ($I_{SG,TN}$)	The ratio between the recovered sludge and the wastewater from the process	Micro	(Molina-Sánchez et al., 2018)
Technological nutrient performance for water ($I_{W,TN}$)	The ratio between the recovered water and the wastewater from the process	Micro	(Molina-Sánchez et al., 2018)
MFA evaluation indexes and intensity efficiency index	Uses material flow analysis and intensity efficiency indexes of MFA based on resource consumption per capita and per 100,000 RMB of GDP	Meso	(Gao et al., 2020)
Resource productivity indicator	Ration between the industrial added value in the value chain and the inputs of materials.	Meso	(Kusumo et al., 2022)
Domestic material consumption	The total amount of materials used in an economy directly (exports are excluded), in tons per capita	Macro	(Horvath et al., 2019)
Resource productivity	The ratio between the gross domestic product (GDP) and domestic material consumption	Macro	(Horvath et al., 2019)

			(Vuta et al., 2018)
Package to Product (PtP) %	Ratio of the climate impact of the packaging to that of the product	Macro	(Poconi et al., 2024)
I₁	Ratio (on an annual basis) between the economic value of the wood harvested per cubic meter and the forest area (reduce)	Macro	(Pieratti et al., 2019)
I₂	CO ₂ emissions of the phase of the forest-wood chain covering the felling to transport for unit volume kgCO ₂ m ⁻³	Macro	(Pieratti et al., 2019)
Statistical entropy analysis (SEA)	SEA is a method to evaluate a material flow system in terms of its ability to dilute or concentrate resources throughout its life cycle.	Macro	(Laner et al., 2017)
Material Flow Analysis (MFA)	A method which assesses flows and stock of materials in a system	Macro	(Kusumo et al., 2022) (Laner et al., 2017)
Material Flow Monitor (MFM)	The MFM is a physical supply and use table, building on national economic and environmental accounting statistics	Macro	(Delahaye et al., 2023)

Table 13: Overview of the identified indicators targeting efficient use of resources

3.3.2 Wastes and residues

Ten indicators were identified targeting waste, mainly focusing on the amounts of waste produced but also the efficiency of certain processes in terms of waste generation (Table 14).

The study by Lokesh et al. (2020) introduces the Waste Factor (WF) and Circular-Process Waste Factor (CPWF). WF measures the ratio of waste—whether solid, liquid, or gaseous—generated as process waste or losses from the system to the amount of end-product and co-product produced by the same process. It is relevant for linear processes. WF is calculated using the following formula:

$$WF = \frac{M_{TotW}}{M_{Prod} + M_{Co.prod}} \quad (17)$$

Where:

- M_{TotW} is the total mass of waste generated from the production process (kg)
- M_{Prod} is the total mass of the end-product as a result of the process (kg)
- $M_{Co.prod}$ is the total mass of useful co-products created as a result of the process (kg)

For circular processes, the CPWF should be used. The CPWF includes, in addition to the end-product and co-product, the mass of recovered or recycled material from the production waste and end-of-life (EOL) in kilograms. It is calculated using the following formula:

$$CPWF = \frac{M_{TotW}}{M_{Prod} + M_{Co.prod} + M_{re.mat}} \quad (18)$$

Where,

- $M_{re.mat}$ is the total mass of recovered or recycled material in kg from the production waste and EOL

The study by Poponi et al. (2024) assessed the circular potential of a Bio-District by applying indicators for waste management. The study uses a dashboard of 10 indicators covering both waste and energy aspects. The selection of indicators is based on a review of circularity indicators relevant to the agri-food sector (Poponi et al., 2022). The economic food loss and waste indicator targets both waste and economic aspects, as it measures the economic impact of wasted food. It is calculated using the following formula:

$$EFLW_i = \sum_j FLW_{i,j} \cdot V_{i,j} \quad (19)$$

Where:

- $FLW_{i,j}$ is the waste of food commodities and food losses belonging to food category (i) for each stage of the supply chain (j), covering agricultural production, post-harvest handling and storage, processing and packaging, distribution, and household consumption (Garcia-Herrero et al., 2019).
- $V_{i,j}$ is the economic values of the food losses and waste for the different categories (i) and at the different stages of the supply chain (j) (Garcia-Herrero et al., 2019).

The article by Kusumo et al. (2022) introduces the wastewater circonomics index, developed by Kayal et al. (2019). The wastewater circonomics index is a composite indicator combining three indicators: the wastewater production efficiency indicator, the composite wastewater reuse indicator, and the wastewater recycling indicator (Kayal et al., 2019). All three indicators are based on the economic value of wastewater efficiency, wastewater reuse, and wastewater recycling (Kayal et al., 2019).

The article by Wozniak et al. (2021) applies indicators related to the circular economy, sustainable development, and Europe 2020 from the Eurostat database to evaluate circular economy development factors in the EU and Poland. The Eurostat database covers several indicators related to both waste generation and waste management.

The article by Horvalth et al. (2019) also applies two waste indicators from the Eurostat database: waste per domestic material consumption (DMC) and waste per Gross Domestic Product (GDP), both based on Eurostat data.

The study by Poponi et al. (2024) assessed the circular potential of a Bio-District by applying indicators for waste management. The study uses a dashboard of 10 indicators covering both waste and energy aspects. The selection of indicators is based on a review of circularity indicators relevant to the agri-food sector (Poponi et al., 2022). The economic food loss and waste indicator targets both waste and economic aspects, as it measures the economic impact of wasted food. It is calculated using the following formula:

$$EFLW_i = \sum_j FLW_{i,j} \cdot V_{i,j} \quad (20)$$

Where,

- $FLW_{i,j}$ are the waste of food commodities and food losses belonging to food category (i) for each stage of the supply chain (j), covering agricultural production, post-harvest handling and storage, processing and packaging, distribution, and household consumption (Garcia-Herrero et al., 2019).
- $V_{i,j}$ are the economic values of the food losses and waste for the different categories (i) and at the different stages of the supply chain (j) (Garcia-Herrero et al., 2019).

The study by Poponi et al. (2024) also assesses the impact of food waste by considering the nutritional value of the waste. It introduces the Nutrient Rich Food Score (NRF9.3) and the Nutritional Cost Foodprint (NCF). The NRF9.3 measures the impact or loss of nutritional value due to food losses. More specifically, it covers (Vázquez-Rowe et al., 2020):

- Macronutrients: Protein and fiber,

- Vitamins A,C and E,
- Minerals: Ca, Fe, Mg and K and
- Three nutrients to be limited: saturated fat, added sugar and Na

It is calculated using the following formula:

$$NRF9.3 = \sum_i w_i \left(\sum_{l=9} \frac{NR_l}{DV_l} \cdot 100 - \sum_{m=3} \frac{LIM_m}{MRV_l} \cdot 100 \right) \quad (21)$$

Where:

- NR is the intake of nutrient l
- DV is the daily recommended value of nutrient l
- LIM is the intake of nutrients to be limited
- MRV is the maximum daily intake of nutrient b to be limited
- W_i is the weighting factor of food category i

Nutrient Cost Footprint (NCF) combines the NRF9.3 and EFLW and measures the overall nutritional and economic impact due to food waste. The values are normalized, and NCF is calculated using the following formula:

$$NCF_i = \alpha_i \cdot \frac{NRF9.3_i}{\overline{NRF9.3}} \cdot \beta_i \frac{EFLW_i}{\overline{EFLW}} = \alpha_i \cdot N_i^* + \beta_i \cdot C_i^* \quad (22)$$

Where,

- $\overline{NRF9.3}$ is the reference value of NRF9.3
- \overline{EFLW} is the reference value of EFLW
- N_i is the normalized value of the nutritional impact
- C_i is the normalized economic impact
- α_i is the weighting factor for the normalized value of the nutritional impact
- β_i is the weighting factor for the normalized economic impact

The article by Poponi et al. (2024) also introduces a waste sent to landfill indicator (WSL). WSL is calculated using the following formula:

$$WSL = \frac{\text{Discarded product}}{\text{Total finished products}} \text{ (kg/ tonnes of finished product)} \quad (23)$$

The indicator introduced by Pagotto and Halog (2016) is used in this publication to assess the circularity of agri-food systems.

Waste Factor (WF)	WF is the ratio of waste from process waste or losses from the system and the amount of end-	Micro	(Lokesh et al., 2020)
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Circular-process waste factor (CPWF)	product and co-product produced. CPWF is the ratio of waste from process waste or losses from the system and the amount of end-product, co-product produced and recovered/ recycled material.	Micro	(Lokesh et al., 2020)
Wastewater circconomics index	Combines the economic value from wastewater efficiency, reuse and recycling	Meso	(Kusumo et al., 2022)
Waste (total)	Refers to the waste indicators from EuroStat data.	Macro	(Woźniak et al., 2021)
Waste (DMC)	Share of all generated waste from DMC and based on EuroStat data.	Macro	(Horvath et al., 2019)
Waste (GDP)	Ratio of generated waste to GDP kg per EUR based on EuroStat data.	Macro	(Horvath et al., 2019)
Waste sent to landfill (WSL)	The ratio between discarded product and total finished product	Macro	(Poponi et al., 2024)
Nutrient rich food score (NRF9.3) (score/ 100 kcal)	Measures the loss of nutritional value due to food waste	Macro	(Poponi et al., 2024)
Nutrient cost footprint (NCF)(unit)	Measures the overall nutritional and economic impact related to food waste	Macro	(Poponi et al., 2024)
Economic Food Loss and Waste indicators (EFLW)	The indicator measures the economic value of food loss and waste.	Macro	(Poponi et al., 2024)

Table 14: Overview of identified indicators targeting waste and residues

3.3.3 Additional Indicators on Waste, Residues, and Textiles

In addition to the waste and residues indicators identified in the systematic literature review, further indicators and metrics can be considered for bio-based systems. A review article by Deus et al. (2019) identified solid waste indicators and their application in waste management. These indicators include general measures such as traditional LCA impact categories (climate change, ecotoxicity, ozone layer depletion, acidification, and eutrophication), landfill volumes, environmental costs, waste generation, composting, recycling, incineration,

risk and impact assessment, zero waste, gaseous emissions, energy recovery, net recovery index, transport intensity index, and economic costs.

Another study by Papamichael et al. (2022) examined the role of gamification in waste management and employed metrics such as waste compositional analysis, municipal solid waste production, municipal solid waste recycling, waste production rate, waste recovery rate, waste generation rate, waste infrastructure, clean index, accumulation rate, accumulation index, air pollution, green space, renewable energy, and waste treatment plans. Hence, for bio-based systems where the focus is on assessing waste and residues, it is possible to supplement with these types of indicators and metrics.

Specifically for textile waste and residues, the European Environmental Agency uses indicators such as total generation of textile waste, proportion of textiles and shoes in mixed municipal waste, effectiveness of the collection system, and pre-sorting at source (European Environmental Agency, 2024). Beyond waste and residues, a study by Suarez-Visbal et al. (2024) applied circularity indicators such as influx of new and second-hand material, percentage of waste generation, and recirculation (number of times a product was recirculated) to assess ten business cases in the textile sector.

3.4 Indicators targeting - Ensure regeneration of natural systems

Regenerate is according to ISO 59004, a process to improve or restore a degraded ecosystem (ISO, 2024a, p. 12). An important component of biodegradable materials is their ability to decompose and thereby support the regeneration of ecosystems (Navare et al., 2021). Hence, maintaining carbon and nutrient cycles is key to ensure that biomass production systems remain healthy (Vural Gursel et al., 2022). The circularity indicators identified targeting regeneration, were consequently categorized into four sub-categories: generic indicators targeting regeneration, sustainable sourcing, maintaining carbon cycles (including carbon sequestration), and maintaining nutrient cycles.

The study by Li et al. (2021) focuses on the utilization of wood biomass and introduces two indexes relevant for generation of natural systems: forest resources and land use change in their evaluation index. The purpose of the evaluation index is to evaluate environmental, social and economic aspects of regional circularity when using wood biomass.

The article by Costa et al. (2023) investigated forms of circularity within an Alpine collective ownership. The article introduces two types of circularity: network-based and forest-based circularity. Forest-based circularity covers sustainable yields and sourcing, cascading, and recycling of wood. Network-based circularity covers more social aspects of circularity. In total, six indicators are proposed covering sustainable sourcing and yield and are explained in table 13.

The study by Horvath et al. (2019) uses the biocapacity and Ecological Footprint (EF) indicators developed by the Global Footprint Network to measure circular efficiency. More specifically, they use biocapacity and ecological footprint for both production and consumption. Biocapacity measures the biologically productive land and sea area available to provide the resources needed and absorb the waste using present technologies and management practices (Borucke et al., 2013). EF measures the biologically productive land needed to provide for the different demands people have (Borucke et al., 2013). These demands include land for growing food, producing fibers, regenerating timber, absorbing carbon dioxide from fossil fuels, and accommodating infrastructure (Borucke et al., 2013).

The article by Wozniak et al. (2021) factors relevant to the development of the bioeconomy and selects indicators relevant for assessing social, environmental, and economic aspects. The indicators are based on the EuroStat database and are therefore easily accessible. The article covers three indicators relevant for assessing the regeneration of natural systems: forest cover, the surface of terrestrial sites designated under Natura 2000, and the total area under organic farming.

Indicators	Description	Level	Reference
Land use change	No further details provided	Meso	(Li et al., 2021)
Forest resources	No further details provided	Meso	(Li et al., 2021)
Sustainable sourcing and yield	Amount of timber harvested/ amount of replanting	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Amount of certified forest biomass and residues (e.g. wood pellets)	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Length of managed forest tracks	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Difference between regrown and cut trees	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Size of the area of habitat destroyed by timber harvesting; loss of productive area	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Amount of trees removed after storms to avoid biotic forest damage	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
Biocapacity	Regeneration capacity of local ecosystems (Global Hectare per capita)	Macro	(Horvath et al., 2019)
Ecological footprint (EF)(production)	The amount of ecological footprint used for production of service and goods (Global Hectare per capita)	Macro	(Horvath et al., 2019)
Ecological footprint (EF) (consumption)	The amount of ecological footprint used for consumption of services and goods (Global Hectare per capita)	Macro	(Horvath et al., 2019)
Surface of terrestrial sites designated under Natura 2000	No further details provided	Macro	(Woźniak et al., 2021)
Total area under organic farming	No further details provided	Macro	(Woźniak et al., 2021)
Forest coverage (Eurostat)	The ratio of the forest area to the total geodesic area of the given territorial unit.	Macro	(Woźniak et al., 2021)

Table 15: Generic indicators targeting regeneration of biobased system identified in the review

3.4.1 Maintaining carbon cycles- coordination with task 2.1

Four publications were identified covering indicators that focus on maintaining carbon cycles and sequestration, as presented in Table 14.

Only one publication covered indicators at the micro level (Corona et al., 2022). The article provided two indicators for biogenic carbon storage in products (BCS₁₀₀ and cBCS). The Biogenic Carbon Storage (BCS₁₀₀) covers the total amount of biogenic carbon stored over a period of 100 years in kg C. This also includes successive loops of recycling. It implies that the result is not given per functional unit, which is normal in a LCA context, but over a period of 100 years. The circular Biogenic Carbon Storage (c-BCS) covers the share of carbon which can be considered circular, meaning the amount of carbon recycled or reused after one recycling

cycle. So, instead of 100 years in the BCS100 the c-BCS covers one cycle of reuse or recycling. Both indicators handle successive loops of reuse or recycling by system expansion.

The two indicators are calculated using the following formulas (Corona et al., 2022, p. 4):

$$BCS_{100}(kgC) = \sum_i \left[CC_i - LU_i - LR_i + PS_i \cdot \left(\frac{100}{LT} - 1 \right) \right] \quad (24)$$

$$c - BCS(kgC) = \sum_i \left[rr_i (CC_i - LU_i - LR_i - PS_i) \cdot \frac{2LT}{100} \right] + CCr_i \cdot \frac{2LT}{100} \quad (25)$$

Where:

- CC_i is the biogenic carbon content in each material i contained in the product, comprising also recycled materials in kg per FU
- LU_i is the loss of biogenic carbon in each material i caused using the product in kg per FU
- LR_i is the loss of biogenic carbon in each material i caused by the recycling or disposal process of the product in kg per FU
- PS_i is the biogenic carbon in every material i which is permanently stored at the EoL of the product per FU. For a material to be considered permanently stored it needs to be stored for 100 years.
- LT is the lifetime of the product in years (max 100 years)
- rr_i is the recycling rate of every material i at the end of life
- CCr_i is the biogenic carbon in the recycled material input in kg per FU

The two indicators focus on carbon storage in the product and are thereby more focused on carbon sequestering in products and less on maintaining carbon systems in the biological system. The two indicators were applied on a comparative case study of lignin-based and bitumen-based asphalt in combination with additional indicators such as MCI, climate change impact using LCA, life cycle costs and environmental cost indicator. The study showed that it provides a more holistic picture of circularity and environmental sustainability of products to combine LCA indicators with additional circularity metrics based on lifecycle thinking. However, it can be challenging to select the right combination of indicators for the specific case in question, and to assess their relative importance. This calls for more standardisation of the relative importance of the different types of indicators.

From the standpoint of dynamic carbon footprint (as studied in task 2.1), these two indicators, BCS100 and cBCS, have also as initial scope to characterize biogenic carbon storage. They are more simplistic to compute but many issues can be raised regarding their consistency, soundness and accuracy. First, the parameters of these equations (CC , LU & LR) do not cover any temporal specification nor are they multiplied with any duration parameter, which beg to differ how this could be then the claimed “amount of biogenic carbon stored over a period of 100 years”. Second, the longer the lifetime of the product, the lower the BCS100 score, which seems contradictory, but this is not the case for c-BCS. Third, only one lifetime is considered, whereas the lifetime can differ over loops (e.g. recycling). Fourth, each process has a duration, not only the use phase (i.e. covered by the lifetime). Fifth, the arbitrariness of the year 100 and the lack of implications. There are other issues as well but latter five are already some. In a dynamic carbon footprint, all such aspects would or could be handled. Even simplistic dynamic carbon footprint, which cover only the foreground process duration, would capture a more accurate image. As often, the simplicity of these equations is their benefit, it comes at a dire cost of loss in soundness, consistency and accuracy, with the alternative dynamic carbon footprint being already quite advanced and amply executed.

At the meso level, two publications covered three indicators targeting maintaining carbon cycles (Li et al., 2021; Lim et al., 2019). The study by Li et al. (2021) examines evaluation indicators for regional circulation symbiosis zones for woody biomass. The study identifies 10 indexes covering environment, economy, society and forest

and resources and CO₂ absorption. The two indicators or indexes provided in relation to carbon cycles are carbon stock and CO₂ sequestered in the trees. The carbon stock is calculated based on the following formula:

$$C = \sum_j \{ [V_j \cdot D_j \cdot BEF_j] \cdot (1 + R_j) \cdot CF \} \quad (26)$$

Where:

- C is the carbon stock amount
- V is the volume of the thinned wood
- D is the volume density of the thinned wood (t-d.m./m³)
- BEF is the biomass expansion factor for the specific tree species
- R is the ratio of the underground to above ground for the specific tree species
- CF is the carbon content per dry matter weight (t.C./t-d.m.)
- J is the tree species

The CO₂ sequestered in the wood is then calculated based on the molecular composition (44/12) and the amount of carbon accumulated. This latter indicator is sound and informative, but lacks the temporal dimension of storage duration, nor relates with any direct process, e.g. recycling.

The study by Lim et al. (2019) examines circular sustainability optimization model for oil crops feedstock systems by using an element targeting approach. The study uses different sustainability indexes to select the best usage of diverse oil crops. The indexes covered are land use, carbon footprint, deforestation, water usage, fertilizer usage, cost calculations and circular carbon element. The total circular carbon element score (TCCE) is assessed based on the carbon emission per land used and the carbon fixation per land use and is calculated based on the following equation:

$$TCCE = \sum_{i=1}^I \left(\frac{Demand \cdot X_i}{Y_i} \cdot C_i \right) \quad (27)$$

Where:

$$C_i = C_{emit_i} - Carbonfix_i \quad \forall i \in I \quad (28)$$

- C_{emit_i} is the carbon emission per land used
- C_{fix_i} is the carbon fixation per land used.
- Y_i is the oil yield per unit of land used for each crop
- i is the total land usage for plantation
- X_i is the utilization ratio of each crop
- Demand represents the demand of bio-diesel at bio-diesel mixing plant

The selected indicators in the study by Lim et al. (2019) is applied in a case study. The case study is a processing plant for biodiesel mixing and utilization and covers four different oil crops (palm oil, soybean oil, rapeseed oil, and sunflower seed oil). This above indicator seems quite contradictory, as a lower yield (meaning more land use) and more net carbon emissions (emission – fixation) would mean a higher total circular carbon element score. Lowering emissions and increase productivity should be incentivized instead. Finally, it is very strange that this is specified as “circular carbon element” since no circularity is covered by this score.

To conclude, considering insights from task 2.1, the only indicator that seems sound is the carbon stock (and CO₂) absorption by Li et al. (2021), although its added value and relevance is limited, especially by just giving a snapshot, i.e. not covering temporal aspects. A dynamic carbon footprint, considering its streamlining in

scientific literature, seems a more appropriate approach to cover these aspects. See deliverable D2.1 for more information.,

Indicators	Description	Level	Reference
Biogenic carbon storage (BCS100 and cBCS)	<p>The two indicators focus on biogenic carbon stored by each product and do not consider other GHG emissions and removals over the life cycle of the product.</p> <p>In line with harmonized LCA</p> <p>BCS₁₀₀ measures the total amount of biogenic carbon stored over a period of 100 years.</p> <p>Circular BCS indicates to what extent biogenic carbon is stored following the CE principles (one cycle)</p>	Micro	(Corona et al., 2022)
Carbon stock	The carbon accumulation amount in the bulk density of the thinned wood.	Meso	(Li et al., 2021)
CO₂ absorption	The amount of CO ₂ absorbed was calculated by taking into account its molecular composition based on the amount of carbon accumulated.	Meso	(Li et al., 2021)
Circular carbon element	The difference between carbon emission per land use and the carbon fixation per land use.	Meso	(Lim et al., 2019)

Table 16: Overview of the indicators identified focus on maintaining carbon cycles and sequestration

3.4.2 Maintaining nutrient cycles

In total, six indicators were identified focused on nutrient cycles - all at the meso or macro level (Table 17).

The article by Poponi et al. (2024) introduces the nutrient circularity indicator (NCI). The indicator is developed by Cobo et al. (2018) and is used to assess circularity in food waste management. The article by Cobo et al. (2018) examines trade-offs between nutrient circularity and environmental impact when managing organic waste. The NCI is defined as the amount of nutrient (nitrogen and phosphorus) which is recycled, applied to land, and taken up by plants (in this case, corn) with respect to the amount of nutrient in the collected organic waste (Cobo et al., 2018). The specific equation is not provided in the article or in the supplementary material.

The article by Perez-Mercado et al. (2022) examines the potential of renewable stocks (livestock manure and human excreta) to meet nutrient deficits in the Bolivian agri-food system. It introduces two indicators: the nutrient circularity indicator and the nutrient sufficiency indicator. The nutrient sufficiency indicator is based on a mass balance calculation and expresses whether there is a nutrient balance between input and output. It focuses on nitrogen and phosphorus.

$$\text{Nutrient sufficiency indicator} = \sum_{i=1}^n \text{Input}_i \cdot \text{Efficiency}_i - \sum_{j=1}^{45} \text{Harvested.produce} \quad (29)$$

Where:

- Input is the amount of nutrient applied to the soil, covering synthetic fertilizer, crop residues, biological fixation, and animal manure.
- Efficiency is the proportion of the input which is available for the crops.
- Harvested.produce is the mass of nutrient taken up by the crop.

- J is the crop.

The nutrient circularity indicator expresses the extent to which a system decreases or removes waste by recirculating it as a product or a raw material. It is calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Nutrient circularity indicator} = \frac{\sum \text{recirculated.Input}}{\sum \text{Input}} \quad (30)$$

Where:

- Recirculated.Input is the sum of nutrients in the recirculated input that are used for crop cultivation.

The article by Gómez-Sagasti et al. (2018) examines phytomanagement of degraded soils and the role organic amendments can play. It discusses the benefits, risks, and uncertainties from the application of organic amendments to soils, covering composts, food residues and wastes, green manure and crop residues, animal manures, municipal biosolids, and wastes from manufacturing processes. The article proposes a set of robust indicators and minimum data to monitor environmental benefits and risks in relation to the organic management of degraded land. These relate to the physical, chemical, and biological properties of the soil and are detailed in Table 17

Indicators	Description	Level	Reference
Nutrient circularity indicator (NCI)	The ratio between the nutrient recycled, applied to land and taken up by plants and the amount of nutrient in the organic waste.	Macro	(Poponi et al., 2024)
Nutrient circularity indicator	Ratio between the recirculated input and the total amount of nutrient applied for crop cultivation	Macro	(Perez-Mercado et al., 2022)
Nutrient sufficiency indicator (NSI)	Expresses whether there is a nutrient balance between input and output	Macro	(Perez-Mercado et al., 2022)
Soil physical properties	Cover aspects such as texture, rooting depth, infiltration, aggregated stability, bulk density, and water holding capacity	Macro	(Gómez-Sagasti et al., 2018)
Soil chemical properties	Cover aspects such as total and/or particulate organic matter, or total C and N, pH, EC and extractable N,P and K	Macro	(Gómez-Sagasti et al., 2018)
Soil biological properties	Cover aspects such as	Macro	(Gómez-Sagasti et al.,

	microbial biomass C and N, soil respiration and enzyme activities, microbial functional and structural diversity, potentially mineralizable N, plant bioassays and earthworm populations.	2018)
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Table 17: Identified indicator related to maintaining nutrient cycles

3.5 Recirculate

According to the article by Vural Gursel et al. (2022), recirculate covers strategies for both chemical and mechanical recycling, maximization of use (durability), and reuse. Therefore, this circular economy principle also largely covers biological products that enter the technical cycle. As we know from the butterfly model (Figure 1), this includes recycling, reconditioning, remanufacturing, reuse, repair and maintenance, and longer lifespan.

The article by Wiedemann et al. (2022) applies the Circular Transition Indicator (CTI) v.10 to assess the circularity of textiles based on renewable and non-renewable fibers. The indicator is developed by the World Business Council for Sustainable Development and is presented in the format of a web-based tool. CTI focuses on the circular and linear mass that flows through a company. CTI provides several indicators covering:

- **Close the loop** which covers % circular inflow, % circular outflow, % water circularity, % renewable energy.
- **Optimize the loop** which covers % critical material and % recovery type.
- **Value of the loop** which covers circular material productivity.

This also implies that the indicator mainly covers the recirculation of materials and renewable energy. For this reason, the indicator is categorized as a recirculation indicator. It is a generic tool that does not have a specific focus on biobased systems.

The study by Spierling et al. (2019) applies the Circular Performance Indicator (CPI) developed by Huysman et al. (2017). The CPI is defined as the ratio of the actual obtained environmental benefit from the used waste treatment option to the ideal environmental benefit according to the quality. The CPI is calculated using the following formula:

$$CPI = \frac{\text{actual benefit}}{\text{Ideal benefit according to quality}} \quad 31$$

The environmental benefit is expressed as natural resource consumption and can be calculated based on LCAs.

The product-level circularity metric mentioned in the article by Kusumo et al. (2022) was originally developed by Linder et al. (2017). Circularity is defined as the fraction of products that come from used parts, and the metric is based on economic value. More specifically, the metric is calculated using the following equation:

$$c = \frac{\text{economic value of recirculated parts}}{\text{economic value of all parts}} \quad (32)$$

Here, a commonly used way to estimate economic value is by using market prices.

The Circular Material Use rate (CMU) is applied in the study by Horvath et al. (2019), where they strive to assess the rebound risk of closed loops. CMU is the ratio of recycled material to the total material in use,

expressed as a percentage. The circular material use rate is developed and provided by EuroStat.

The article by Kusumo et al. (2022) includes the Recyclability Benefit Rate (RBR) in their framework to assess circularity. The RBR is based on Huysman et al. (2015) which in turn is based on Ardente and Mathieux (2014). The indicator is expressed as the potential environmental savings from recycling a product divided by the environmental burdens of virgin production and subsequent disposal.

In the framework to assess circularity by Kusumo et al. (2022), a longevity indicator is also covered. The longevity indicator is developed by Franklin-Johnson et al. (2016) and is applied to production from the technical cycle (mobile phone handsets). It covers three elements: (A) the initial lifetime of the product, (B) the contribution from the refurbished lifetime, and (C) the contribution from the recycled lifetime. The indicator does not have a specific focus on biobased products.

The indicator is calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Longevity} = A + B + C \quad (33)$$

Where,

$$B = (B_1 + B_2) \quad (34)$$

$$B_1 = (w_1 \cdot x_1 \cdot U_1) \quad (35)$$

$$B_2 = (w_1 \cdot x_1 \cdot w_2 \cdot x_2 \cdot U_2) \quad (36)$$

$$C = C_1 + C_2 \quad (37)$$

$$C_1 = (A + B_1 + B_2) \cdot \left[\frac{w_1 \cdot x_1 \cdot z_1}{1 - w_1 \cdot y_1 \cdot z_1} \right] \quad (38)$$

$$C_2 = (A + B_1 + B_2) \cdot \left[\frac{w_1 \cdot x_1 \cdot w_2 \cdot y_2 \cdot z_2}{1 - w_1 \cdot x_1 \cdot w_2 \cdot y_2 \cdot z_2} \right] \quad (39)$$

- A is the initial lifetime
- w is the percentage of products returned
- x is the percentage of products refurbished
- U is the lifetime expressed in months
- y is the percentage of recycled product
- z is the percentage of unrecovered material
- 1,2 represents the two cycles but an infinite number of cycles can be added

The article by Kusumo et al. (2022) also includes the recycling index presented by Reuter and Schaik (2016) and Reuter et al. (2015). The indicator is provided on an A+++–G scale and is based on the recycling and recovery rate after physical sorting and final treatment processing.

The final micro-level indicator covering recirculate is the length of material use expressed in carbon sequestration time. The indicator is based on the MCI and is further explained in section 3.10. However, the interesting point here is that in the study by Stegmann et al. (2023) carbon sequestration time is applied as a proxy for product lifetime or durability.

The article by Stanchev et al. (2020) introduced the Environmental Circularity Performance Indicators (ECPI) to be used for assessing the environmental performance of circular solutions for anaerobic treatment of dairy processing effluents. The indicator is based on Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) results and is calculated using the following equation:

$$ECPI_{AD}^{Li} = \frac{EB_{Direct}^{Li} + EB_{Indirect}^{Li}}{EC_{Direct}^{Li} + EC_{Indirect}^{Li}} \quad (40)$$

Where:

- EB_{Direct}^{Li} is the direct environmental benefits in relation to the reduced environmental pressure. In this case, it refers to avoided eutrophication and emissions from the disposal of the sludge.
- $EB_{Indirect}^{Li}$ is the indirect environmental benefits from the avoided environmental impact due to the recovered products. In this case, it refers to energy and fertilizer.
- EC_{Direct}^{Li} is the direct environmental cost, such as emitted CH_4 and CO_2 emissions.
- $EC_{Indirect}^{Li}$ is the indirect environmental cost, such as the embodied emissions in the resources used and transportation.
- Li is the level of the environmental assessment on which the results are based.

The material circularity indicator (MCI) was developed by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation in 2015 and was updated in 2019. The original MCI from 2015 covers recirculate. Whether as the update from 2019 also covers regenerate and is therefore categorized as a complex indicator. The MCI is widely adopted, and it is further analysed in section 3.10. Stegmann et al. (2023) also applies the utility function of the MCI, which is also elaborated in section 3.10.

The mixture circularity index (MCI_{RAM}) by da Costa et al. (2024) is a further development of the Material Circularity Index adopted to asphalt mixtures by Mantalovas and Di Mino (2020). The MCI_{RAM} is modified to incorporate a broader set of mechanical parameters to determine the utility factor.

The study by Pieratti et al. (2019) introduces an indicator, denoted I_4 , which can be used for assessing the economic differential (%) gain from a more reasonable valorization of valuable wood assortments. More valuable wood assortments are considered those with a longer lifetime and added value in the supply chain. The idea is that the indicators are used to assess recycling and ensure that the highest value is obtained. I_4 is calculated using the following formula:

$$I_4 = \frac{\text{Potential earnings} - \text{effective earnings}}{\text{Effective earnings}} (\%) \quad (41)$$

The study by Pieratti et al. (2019) also introduces an indicator which are to represent reuse for the forest sector. The indicator is defined as the product life span before the wood is used for energy generation in years.

The article by Vuta et al. (2018) provides an assessment of the impact of the circular economy on economic growth. It proposes several macro-level indicators targeting recycling, including recycling rates for municipal waste, packaging waste, and bio-waste. Bio-wastes are raw materials that are composted in agriculture. The data is based on the EUROSTAT database.

Indicators	Description	Level	Reference
WBC circularity indicator (%)	The Circular Transition Indicator (CTI) v.10 focuses on the circular and linear mass that flows through a company. It covers mainly the recirculation of materials and water but also the use of renewable energy.	Micro	(Wiedemann et al., 2022)

Circular economy performance Indicators (CPI)	Is the quotient of the actual environmental benefits of the current applied waste treatment and the ideal environmental benefit according to quality.	Micro	(Spierling et al., 2019)
Product-level circularity metric	It is the ratio between the economic value of recirculated parts over economic value of all parts.	Micro	(Kusumo et al., 2022)
Recyclability benefit rate	The ratio between the environmental savings associated with recycling and the environmental burdens of virgin production and disposal.	Micro	(Kusumo et al., 2022)
Longevity indicator	Measures the material retention based on how long the resource is kept in use. It covers initial lifetime, refurbishment and recycling.	Micro	(Kusumo et al., 2022)
Recycling index	Based on recycling and recovery rates – it is a total weight-based recycling/recovery rate of all elements in a product when the physical sorting and final treatment is carried out. It is provided as a A+++–G scale.	Micro	(Kusumo et al., 2022)
Length of material use expressed in carbon sequestration time	The study is inspired by the MCI from 2015. However, only the utility function is included. In the study, the length of material use is expressed as carbon sequestration time.	Micro	(Stegmann et al., 2023)
Environmental Circularity Performance Indicator (ECPI)	The ratio between the direct and indirect environmental benefits and the direct and indirect environmental impacts as a result of the anaerobic digestion	Micro	(Stanchev et al., 2020)
Material Circularity Indicator (MCI)	The MCI measures to which extent linear flows are reduced, to which extent restorative flows are maximized and how long and intensively the product is used compared to an industry-average	Micro	(Escribà-Gelonch et al., 2023; Kusumo et al., 2022; Razza et al., 2020; Rocchi et al., 2021; Stegmann et al., 2023)
Material utility (MU) Indicator	The study is inspired by the MCI from 2015. However, only the utility function is included. Where the material use intensity and the length of the material use is assessed separately.	Micro	(Stegmann et al. 2023)
Mixture circularity	Covers the linearity of flow (which is	Micro	(da Costa et al., 2024)

index (MCI_{RAM})	the proportion of reused or recycled materials) and the utility of the product. Adaptation of the MCI.		
Circular material use rate (CMU)	CMS is the ratio of recycled material to the total material use in %	Macro	(Horvath et al., 2019)
Recycling rates (R) %	Ratio of the recycled waste to all generated waste, excluding major mineral wastes (%)	Macro	(Horvath et al., 2019)
	Ration of the recycled waste to all waste produced (%)	Macro	(Poponi et al., 2024)
Recycle I₄	The economic differential (%) gain from a more rational valorization of the valuable wood assortments	Macro (sector specific wood)	(Pieratti et al., 2019)
Reuse I₃	Product life span before to be used for energy generation (years)	Macro (sector specific wood)	(Pieratti et al., 2019)
Recycling rate of packaging waste	Based on EUROSTAT database	Macro	(Vuta et al., 2018)
Recycling rate of biowaste	Compostable raw material in agriculture. Based on EUROSTAT database	Macro	(Vuta et al., 2018)
Recycling rate of municipal waste	Based on EUROSTAT database	Macro	(Vuta et al., 2018)

Table 18: Summary of recirculation-related indicators by level and source, based on systematic review

3.6 Extend the high-quality use - including cascading

Within this strategy, the idea is to optimize the time the product, material, and substance spend in the cycle and ensure consecutive cycles while minimizing quality losses. Therefore, this strategy also overlaps with the recirculate strategy (Vural Gursel et al., 2022). To understand the high-quality use of biobased products, the bio-based value pyramid is central (Figure 5). The notion is that the biobased material should first be used at the highest level possible and only as a last resort be used for energy, heat, and fuels (Stegmann et al., 2020).

Figure 5 Bio-based value pyramid based on Stegmann et al. (2020)

In the review, a number of indicators were identified that explicitly refer to cascading, and these are accounted for in this section.

The article by Vamza et al. (2021) proposes a bioresource utilization index to quantify and compare resource efficiency in production. It is calculated using the following formula:

$$B_{\text{uind}} = \frac{(P + BP_1 \cdot c_1 + BP_2 \cdot c_2 + BP_3 \cdot c_3 + BP_4 \cdot c_4 + BP_5 \cdot c_5)}{RM} \quad (42)$$

Where:

- P is the product in kg of dry weight.
- BP_n is the by-product in kg of dry weight.
- c_n is the coefficient assigned to the specific level in the bio-based value pyramid to represent the value of the bioresource utilization.
- RM is the used raw material in kg of dry weight.

In the article by Vamza et al. (2021), the bioresource utilization index was applied to two specific Latvian enterprises. The coefficient used in the case study to represent the value for bioresource utilization was:

- 1 for Pharmaceuticals and fine chemicals
- 0.75 for food and feed
- 0.5 for bioplastic and polymers
- 0.25 for bulk chemicals and biogas
- 0 for energy, heat, and fuels

The article by Costa et al. (2023) proposes accounting indicators that can promote more circular practices

within collective ownerships of forests. Some of these cover cascading use and recycling of wood. Therefore, the indicators also link to the recirculate strategy. The indicators are detailed in Table 19.

The article by Karayilan et al. (2021) evaluates circular economy practices within the plastic packaging value chain. One of the circular economy strategies they consider is the use of bio-based biodegradable plastics. Here, they also consider the amount of directly compostable bio-based biodegradable plastic when calculating the MCI.

Bioresource utilization index	The ratio between the dry weight of the materials used in the product and by-products and the total raw materials used. By the by-products, a weight according to the bio-based value pyramid	Micro	(Vamza et al., 2021)
Cascading use and recycling of wood	Number of families and local organizations using wood for purposes other than burning	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Percentage of raw materials reused to expand biomass availability	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Percentage of raw materials whose direct use is linked to energy production	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Percentage/ volume of wastes and residues that become new resources	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Amount of cooperation with actors that use wood in a cascading manner	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Number of products designed in cooperation with actors that use wood in a cascading manner	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Amount of wood sold to individuals or enterprises using it to make durable products with high added value.	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
Composting	The amount of directly compostable bio-based biodegradable plastic	Macro	(Karayilan et al., 2021)

Table 19: Overview of the identified indicators targeting cascading and high-quality use

3.7 Positive effect on economic viability

The review also revealed several indicators assessing the economic aspects of circularity, which can then be

used to assess if the proposed circular solutions will also have a positive effect on economic viability (table 20).

The article by Corona et al. (2022) assessed the circularity of lignin-based asphalt by using several different indicators including Life Cycle Costs and Environmental Cost Indicators, covering also economic aspects. The two indicators were based on a previous study inaccessible study by Van veen et al. (2021). Consequently, it is not possible to describe the specific LCA and ELCC applied.

The study by Stillitano et al. (2022) proposes a multi-cycle model to measure the sustainability of circular solutions in the agri-food supply chain and apply it to the olive oil sector. To assess the sustainability of the proposed circular solutions they apply Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Environmental Life Cycle Costs (ELCC) and Social Life Cycle Assessment (SLCA). ELCA is based on LCA results using the SimaPro software and applies the Environmental Prices approach (Stillitano et al., 2022).

The article by Kursumo et al. (2022) introduced the Eco-cost value ratio (EVR), which is further unfolded in Scheepens et al. (2016). The Eco-cost value ratio is based on eco-cost, which is a single indicator in LCA. It expresses the costs which is needed to reduce the material depletion and environmental pollution of a product to a level which is in line with the carrying capacity of the Earth (Scheepens et al., 2016). The EVR is then the ratio between the eco-cost and the value of the product. In a simple EVR analysis, the market value is equal to the price of product. However, in the study by Scheepens et al. (2016) the sum of the perceived product- and service- quality along with the image is used as the value.

The study by Li et al. (2021) assessing the circularity of woody biomass also covered two indicators targeting economic aspects this is the collection and transportation cost for carrying out the thinning of the wood and the economic value based on using woody biomass to create electricity and thermal energy.

The study by Lim et al. (2019) assessing diverse oil crop feedstock systems also introduces an indicator targeting economic aspects, namely total costs (TC). The indicator covers the total costs for the production and transport of the crops. The TC is calculated based on the following formula:

$$TC = Transport_{costs} + Production_{costs} \quad (43)$$

Where,

$$Transport_{costs} = \sum_{r,i,p=1}^{R,I,P} (Demand \cdot X_i \cdot RFR \cdot d_{rip}) + \sum_{j=1}^I (demand \cdot X_i \cdot SFR) \quad (44)$$

$$SFR = \frac{Daily\ hire + Port\ Cost + Fuel\ cost + Canel\ dues}{Cargo\ Quantity} \quad (45)$$

$$Production_{costs} = \sum_{j=1}^I (Demand \cdot X_i \cdot P_i) \quad (46)$$

- Demand is the demand of bio-diesel at bio-diesel mixing plant
- X_i is the utilization ratio of each crop
- RFR is the road freight rate
- D_{rip} is the truck traveling distance to deliver oil crops (i) from resource (r) to plant (p)
- SFR is the sea freight rate
- P_i is the production cost of each oil crop

The study by Pieratti et al. (2019) introduces an indicator, I_4 , which can be used for assessing the economic differential (%) gain from a more reasonable valorization of valuable wood assortments. Where more valuable wood assortments are considered, those with a longer lifetime and created added value in the supply chain. The idea is that the indicators are used to assess recycling and to ensure that the highest value is obtained. I_4 is calculated using the following formula:

$$I_4 = \frac{\text{Potential earnings} - \text{effective earnings}}{\text{Effective earnings}} (\%) \quad (47)$$

The article by Vuta et al. (2018) assesses the circular economy's impact on the EU economic growth. Here, it uses a number of indicators related to the economic aspects of circularity. The indicators are all based on data from EuroStat and covers: environmental taxes as a percentage of GDP.

Indicators	Description	Level	Reference
Life Cycle Cost (LCC)	Considers all costs throughout the lifetime of a product.	Micro (generic)	(Corona et al., 2022)
Environmental Life Cycle Costs (ELCC)	Introduced in addition to the direct monetary flows also the monetary value off the externalities.	Micro (generic)	(Corona et al., 2022) (Stillitano et al., 2022)
Eco-cost value ratio (EVR)	The ratio between the environmental pollution cost in monetary terms of the product or service and its value (typically market but can also be perceived value).	Micro but can also be used on Macro level (generic)	(Kusumo et al., 2022)
Collection and transport costs for carrying out the thinned wood	No further explanation provided	Meso (sector specific wood)	(Li et al., 2021)
Creation of economic value based on the production of electricity/ thermal efficiency of woody biomass	No further explanation provided	Meso (sector specific wood)	(Li et al., 2021)
Total costs	Covers to cost for production and transport	Meso (sector specific oil crops)	(Lim et al., 2019)
Environmental tax revenues as a percentage of GDP	Environmental taxes as a percentage of GDP	Macro	(Vuta et al., 2018)
Patents	Patents related to recycling and secondary raw materials in the EU per 1 million	Macro	(Vuta et al., 2018)

Table 20: Overview of the identified indicators covering aspects related to positive effect on economic viability

3.8 Positive effect on social equality

Circular economy is, in some definitions, also linked to social aspects such as creating a positive effect on social equality. The review also revealed indicators targeting more social aspects of the circular economy, as illustrated in Table 21.

The study by Stillitano et al. (2022) proposed a multi-cycled approach to assess the circularity and sustainability of circular solutions. The framework is based on lifecycle assessments (LCA), Environmental Life Cycle Costing (ELCOO), and Social Life Cycle Assessment (SLCA) and is designed for the olive-oil sector. SLCA is a tool that can be used to evaluate the social impact during the life cycle. In the study, the Psychosocial Risk Factor (PRF) impact pathway is used. This method quantifies the risk of psychosocial impacts on different types of stakeholders, taking into consideration the duration of exposure to certain working and living conditions, which can result in health issues (Stillitano et al., 2022).

The article by Li et al. (2021) introduced two indicators targeting socially related aspects, such as the number of jobs created by forestry employees and the amount of food supply. The article targets the circularity of woody biomass.

The article by Costa et al. (2023) investigates circularity in an Alpine collective ownership. It provides a comprehensive framework of indicators to assess forms of circularity, covering network-based circularity and forest-based circularity. Network-based circularity refers to the cooperation, social networks, and coordination between different associations or institutions to support the local community and territory, focusing on networks and relationships. Hence, it is related to the more social aspects of circularity. The framework includes a considerable number of indicators covering aspects such as rural economy and managerial autonomy, the subsidiarity principle, the primacy of communities over individuals, and circularity within generations.

The article by Fernández Ocamica et al. (2024) provides an assessment of the European bio-based economy using a set of environmental, socioeconomic, and technical indicators. One of the sources used is the Social Progress Index (SPI). The SPI is based on 60 indicators covering environmental and social aspects, such as:

- **Basic human needs:** Nutrition and basic medical care, water and sanitation, shelter, and personal safety;
- **Foundations of wellbeing:** Access to basic knowledge, access to information and communication, health and wellness, and environmental quality;
- **Opportunity:** Personal rights, personal freedom and choice, inclusiveness, and access to advanced education.

SLCC	A tool to evaluate the social impacts occurring during the life cycle. In the study the psychosocial Risk Factor (PRF) is used.	Mirco	(Stillitano et al., 2022)
Number of jobs created by forestry employees	No further details provided	Meso	(Li et al., 2021)
Amount of food supply	The study focuses on woody biomass and cover aspects such as bamboo shorts	Meso	(Li et al., 2021)

Network-based circularity: Rural economy and managerial autonomy	Number of members operatively involved in the governance/ hectares of territory managed	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Wood distributed to collective ownership's members/ total wood managed	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Value of wood distributed to collective ownerships' members/ total value of wood managed	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Number of members benefitting from collective ownerships' wood cut	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Number of members benefitting from the reuse of waste/ wood	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Number of members participating in the replanting of trees	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Number of members cleaning the forest	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
Network-based circularity: Subsidiarity principle	Number of buildings managed by collective ownership in favour of the local community	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Number of members using collective ownerships' infrastructure and buildings	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Number of members involved in organizing local events	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Number of members participating in local events	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Number of members involved in offering cultural exhibitions	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Number of members participating in cultural exhibitions	Meso	((Costa et al., 2023)
	Number of members that voluntarily support and participate in organizing collective ownerships' initiatives regarding forest maintenance	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
Network-based circularity: The primacy communities over individuals	Number of collective ownerships' decisions that favour the community at the expense of specific individual benefits	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Number of initiatives in favor of the conservation and maintenance of the local infrastructure and environment	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Amount of overproduced wood reused in	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)

Network-based circularity: Circularity within generations	favour of local activities		
	Amount of wood used to maintain and improve the safety of local mountain trails	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Number of educational activities offered	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Number of members involved in educational activities	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Number of members benefitting from educational activities regarding the cascading use of wood and reuse raw material to expand biomass	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Analysis of the age of people involved in educational activities and the attendees	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Number of young people voluntarily involved in the collective ownerships' activities in favor of the forest	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Number of members involved in the collective ownerships' activities in favor of the forest	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Number of members promoting and using recycled wood	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Numbers of young people involved in managing collective ownerships	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
Social progress index (SPI)	Number of young people divided by the total of the members	Meso	(Costa et al., 2023)
	Index of 60 indicators measuring to which extent countries provides their citizens with social and environmental needs.	Macro	(Fernández Ocamica et al., 2024)

Table 21: Overview of identified indicators covering positive effect on social equality

3.9 Complex indicators

In the review, we have made a category named complex indicators this covers indicators covering several different CE principles. An overview is provided in Table 22 and the following section will provide a short explanation of the complex indicators.

The Circular Economy Indicator Prototype (CEIP) is applied in a study by Guevara-Rivera et al. (2021) in combination with simulation modelling on a case study of a confectionery factory. The CEIP is based on an article by Cayzer et al. (2017). CEIP is based on 15 questions targeting material selection, material identification, manufacturing waste management, product packaging, lifetime extension (warranty), product assess, waste reductions and product recovery (Cayzer et al., 2017). Each question is assigned points and based on the score a weighted score is generated.

As mentioned earlier, the MCI indicator from 2019 covers both recirculate and regenerate strategies and is

therefore considered a complex indicator. The update made it more applicable to use in biological systems. The MCI is further elaborated in 3.10.

The article by Wiedemann et al. (2022) applies, in addition to several other circularity indicators, the feedstock content requirements from the Circular Materials Guidelines (CMG) to assess the circularity of renewable and non-renewable fibers. The CMG is developed by Fashion Positive, which is a global non-profit organization working to create a circular transition in the fashion industry. The guideline is for producers of fibers and it defines circular materials. The guideline covers feedstock content, chemistry, water and energy. The guideline provides “better” and “best” categories to create a roadmap for how companies can integrate circularity into fiber development. The guideline builds on existing standards and certification schemes. Many of which can be verified by a 3rd part audit or assessment. For feedstock content, requirements are set for “better” or “best” categories on recycled content or reclaimed content, on renewable sources and recyclability potential. The CMG does not provide a numeric value but a categorization in “better” or “best” and it only covers textile fibers. It will be difficult to apply this to other sectors.

The study by Wiedemann et al. (2022) also applies the Material Reutilization Score (MRS) to assess circularity of renewable and non-renewable fibers. The MRS is developed by cradle to cradle and is part of their certification scheme. It is calculated by using the following formula:

$$MRS = \left(\frac{\% \text{ of the product considered recyclable or compostable} \cdot 2 + \% \text{ of the recycled or rapidly renewable content}}{3} \right) \cdot 100 \quad (48)$$

Thereby the MRS mainly cover the recirculate and renewability strategy.

The study by Spierling et al. (2019) applies the Circular Performance Indicator (CPI) that were first developed by Huysman et al. (2017). The CPI is defined as the ratio of the actual obtained environmental benefit from the used waste treatment option over the ideal environmental benefit according to the quality. The CPI is calculated using the following formula:

$$CPI = \frac{\text{actual benefit}}{\text{Ideal benefit according to quality}} \quad (49)$$

The environmental benefit is expressed as natural resource consumption and can be calculated based on LCA results.

The article by Kusumo et al. (2022) includes the Global Resource Indicator (GRI) in their framework for assessing biological systems. The GRI is further unfolded in the article by Adibi et al. (2017) and it covers availability of resources such as recyclability and geopolitical availability.

$$GRI = \frac{X}{Y \cdot Z} \quad (50)$$

Where,

- X is the scarcity based on CML characterization factors from LCA
- Y is recyclability or quality factors that depends on the diffusion and recycling rates
- Z is the geopolitical availability, and it is based on World Governance Indicator (WGI) index, the number of countries and the standard deviation.

The article by Kowalski et al. (2022) uses a circular economy quality indicator to assess the energy recovery from municipal waste. It introduces the circular economy quality indicator, which is calculated using the following formula:

$$CEI = CE_T + CE_{En} + CE_{Ec} + CE_{Sb} \quad (51)$$

Where:

- CE_T is the technological/ technical option quality indicator

- CE_{En} is the environmental option quality indicator
- CE_{Ec} is the economic option quality indicator
- CE_{sb} is the societal behavior option quality indicator

The quality indicators are based on the degree of validity and an evaluation of the technical, environmental, economic, and social behaviour options. The process for assessing quality indicators is as follows: First, a panel of experts selects options to characterize the production system being evaluated. The experts choose from 18 different options within the four option group frameworks: technological and technical, environmental, economic/business, and societal behaviour. Based on the data supplied by the experts, an arithmetic average value is calculated for each option.

In the study by Adibi et al. (2017) nine resources were considered in terms of availability: cobalt, platinum, iron, aluminum, copper, silver, wood, sand and gravels, dysprosium, europium and neodymium. Hence, only one biobased resource, “wood” is considered in the indicator. Consequently, it might have limited relevance in assessing biobased system unless it is further adopted to biobased systems. However, a method is proposed for adopting CML characterization factors for renewable resources, as they are also often scarce like other materials.

The study by Lim et al. (2019) proposes a sustainability score covering land usage, carbon footprint, deforestation, water use and fertilizer usage to assess oil feedstock systems. The sustainability index is then calculated by comparing the sustainability score of sustainable aspect with the maximum and minimum sustainability score of the crops under consideration.

The CE-eco-innovation scoreboard is mentioned in Kusumo et al. (2022) and is a set of indicators to measure the circularity of regional policy. The scoreboard is developed by Smol et al. (2017) and covers a set of indicators targeting several categories such CE-eco-innovation inputs, CE-eco-innovation activities, CE-eco-innovation outputs, resource efficiency outcomes and socio-economic outcomes. An overview of the indicators is provided in Figure 6.

CE–Eco-innovation inputs

- Regional authorities environmental and energy R&D for CE appropriations and outlays (% of GDP)
- Regional total value of green early stage investments (EURO per capita)

CE–Eco-innovation activities

- Firms having implemented CE–eco-innovation activities aiming at a reduction of material input per unit output (% of total firms in region)
- Firms having implemented CE–eco-innovation activities aiming at a increase of material recycling (% of total firms in region)

CE–Eco-innovation outputs

- Generated industrial waste (amount of waste/ person)
- Generated municipal waste (amount of waste/ person)
- Recycled industrial waste (amount of waste/ person)
- Recycled municipal waste (amount of waste/ person)
- Life cycle assessment of enterprises activity (amount companies with LCA reports per regions)
- Number of companies with "zero waste" program

Resource efficiency outcomes

- Material productivity (regional GDP/Domestic Material Consumption of region)
- Water productivity (regional GDP/Water Footprint of region)
- Energy productivity (regional GDP/gross inland energy consumption of region)
- GHG emissions intensity (CO₂e/regional GDP)

Socio-economic outcomes

- Employment in eco-industries and circular economy (% of total employment across all companies of region)
- Revenue in eco-industries and circular economy (% of total revenue across all companies of region)

Figure 6: Overview of the CE-eco-innovation indicators (Smol et al., 2017, p. 674)(Smol et al., 2017, p. 674)(Smol et al., 2017, p. 674)

The evaluation index system for evaluating the development is mentioned in Kusumo et al. (2022) but originates from Qing et al. (2011). The index is used to assess the circular economy development of the Shaanxi Province. The index system includes 26 indicators covering categories such as social and economic development, resource efficiency, resource recycling and reuse, environmental protection and pollution reduction (Qing et al., 2011).

The OECD Green Growth Indicators are also mentioned in the framework developed in Kusumo et al. (2022). The OECD Green Growth Indicators is a selection of indicators which can be used to monitor the progress towards green growth (OECD, 2017). It does not have a specific focus on circularity but focus on aspects such as the socio-economic context and characteristic of growth, the environmental and resource productivity of the economy, the natural asset base, the environmental dimension of quality of life and economic opportunities and policy responses. Especially the indicators in relation to resource productivity and natural assets base can be relevant in a circular economy context.

Indicators	Description	Level	Reference
Circular Economy Indicator Prototype (CEIP)	CEIP contains fifteen questions evaluating the five cycle stages of a circular supply chain. Each question is then assigned a measurable variable using a weighted score.	Micro	(Guevara-Rivera et al., 2021)
Material Circularity Indicator (MCI) updated in 2019	The MCI is adapted to biological system.	Micro	(Corona et al., 2022; Gallo et al., 2024; Karayilan et

			al., 2021; Wiedemann et al., 2022)
The circularity materials guidelines	The guideline is for producers of fiber and it defines circular materials. The guideline covers feedstock content, chemistry, water and energy. The guideline provides “better” and “best” categories. Does not provide a numerical value.	Micro	(Wiedemann et al., 2022)
Material reutilization score (MRS)	The indicator is calculated based on recyclability of the product, its ability to compost, its recycled content and the content of rapidly renewable material.	Micro	(Wiedemann et al., 2022)
Global Resource Indicators (GRI)	The indicator includes different aspects related to resource availability, such as recyclability and geopolitical availability.	Micro	(Kusumo et al., 2022)
Circular economy quality indicator (CEI)	Arithmetic average value based on an expert scoring of 16 options for each of four option groups: technological and technical, environmental, economic/ business and societal behaviour	Micro	(Kowalski et al., 2022)
Sustainability score	The sustainability score is based on land usage, carbon footprint, deforestation, water usage and fertilizer usage.	Meso	(Lim et al., 2019)
CE-eco-innovation	It is a scoreboard to assess CE-eco-innovation, covering selected indicators on CE-eco-innovation inputs, activities and output and resource efficiency outcomes and socio-economic outcomes at a regional level.	Macro	(Kusumo et al., 2022)
Evaluation index system for evaluating the CE development	It is a selection of indicators to assess circular economy classified according to five categories: Social and economic development, resource efficiency, resource recycling and reuse, environmental protection and pollution reduction	Macro	(Kusumo et al., 2022)
Green growth indicators (OECD)	It is a set of indicators selected by OECD covering the socio-economic context and characteristics of growth, the environment and resource productivity, natural asset base, economic opportunities and policy responses	Macro	(Kusumo et al., 2022)

Table 22: Overview of the identified complex indicators

3.10 The Material Circularity Indicator (MCI)

The MCI was the indicator most used in the articles to assess circularity. Nine articles in the review used the indicator. The first version of the MCI was published in 2015, focusing solely on the technical cycles and

materials from non-renewable origins (Vural Gursel et al., 2023). This also implies that the MCI has been more widely applied within the technical system. In 2019, the MCI was revised, and the scope of the method was extended to also cover the biological system (Godiin et al., n.d.). The update included introducing the fraction of biological material from sustained production into the virgin feedstock part of the MCI. Furthermore, composting and energy recovery of sustained production were included in the calculation of the unrecoverable waste. The articles identified in the review covered both the application of the original MCI from 2015 and the updated MCI from 2019.

Gursel et al. (2023) also carried out a review looking into the studies covering biological systems and their use of the MCI. However, this review will focus more specifically on the adaptations needed to adopt the utility function to products from biobased systems and what other adaptations were needed, especially how sustainable production was categorized. This provides additional insights to existing work.

3.10.1 Description of the material circularity indication

First, the following section will provide a short introduction to the calculation of the MCI based on the version from 2019 (Godiin et al., n.d.). The MCI focuses on the restoration of material flows and can be applied at both the product and company levels. However, the following review will present the calculation at the product level, as the principles are the same. The MCI is designed to take into account six circularity principles: (1) sustained sources of biological materials, (2) feedstock comes from reused or recycled sources, (3) products are kept in use for as long as possible, (4) components and materials are reused and recycled after use, (5) ensuring intensive use of products, and (6) ensuring that biological materials are uncontaminated and biologically available. This also implies that the MCI is one of the more complex indicators to calculate, as many product properties, and several circularity strategies are covered by the assessment.

The MCI measures the extent to which linear flows are minimized and restorative flows maximized in the Linear Flow Index (LFI). Then, it measures how long and how intensively the product is used compared to an industry average in the so-called utility function (X). More specifically, the MCI from 2019 covers three product characteristics (Figure 7):

- The mass V of virgin raw material used in the production
- The mass W of unrecovered waste that is allocated to the product
- The utility function X covering the length and intensity of the product

The MCI measures the circularity levels in a range from 0 to 1, and the calculations are the same regardless of whether the system is closed or open loop. The following will unfold how the MCI is calculated based on the different parts (V , W , LFI and X).

Figure 7: Overview of the elements covered by the MCI (Godijn et al., n.d.)

Calculation of virgin feedstock (V)

Virgin feedstock part of the MCI is calculated using the following equation:

$$V = M(1 - F_R - F_u - F_s) \quad (52)$$

Where:

- M is the mass of the finished product
- F_R is the fraction of feedstock based on recycled sources
- F_u is the fraction deriving from reused sources
- F_s is the fraction of the biological material that comes from sustained production.

The method does not provide specifications on which programs, schemes or indicators can be considered a sustained production. However, it emphasizes aspects such as deforestation, soil degradation and habitat loss as potential impacts which would disrupt the circularity of the material flows. Appropriate chain of custody certifications be selected.

Calculation of the unrecoverable waste (W)

The amount of unrecoverable waste is calculated using the following equation:

$$W = W_0 + \frac{W_F + W_C}{2} \quad (53)$$

Where:

- W_0 is the waste going to landfill or energy recovery
- W_F is the waste generated when the recycled content used in the product is produced
- W_C is the waste generated in the recycling process

The indicator applies a 50:50 approach when allocating between the user of the recycled material and the provider of the recycled material.

W_0 is calculated using the following equation:

$$W_0 = M(1 - C_R - C_U - C_C - C_E) \quad (54)$$

Where.

- C_R is the fraction of mass collected for recycling at end-of-life
- C_U is the fraction of mass used in component reuse
- C_C is the fraction of the uncontaminated biological material that is composted
- C_E is the fraction of biological materials from sustained production used for energy recovery

The waste generated to produce the recycled content (W_F) is calculated using the following formula:

$$W_F = M \frac{(1-E_F)F_R}{E_F} \quad (55)$$

Where:

- E_F is the efficiency of the recycling process used to produce the recycled material used in the product

The waste generated in the recycling process (W_C) is calculated using the following formula:

$$W_C = M(1 - E_C)C_R \quad (56)$$

Where:

- E_C is the efficiency of the recycling process used to recycle the product at its end-of-life

Calculation of the Linear Flow Index (LFI)

The Linear Flow Index (LFI) is a measure of the amount of linear flows going into a product. It covers the materials sourced from virgin materials and the materials ending as unrecoverable waste. LFI is calculated using the following equation:

$$LFI = \frac{V+W}{2M + \frac{W_F - W_C}{2}} \quad (57)$$

The value will be between 1 and 0 where 1 represents an entirely linear flow and 0 an entirely restorative flow.

The utility function (x)

The utility function covers to parts: part one covers the length of the products use phase and the second part covers the intensity of the use.

The utility (X) is calculated using the formula:

$$X = \left(\frac{L}{L_{av}}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{U}{U_{av}}\right) \quad (58)$$

Where:

- L is the lifetime of the product
- L_{av} is the lifetime of the industry average
- U is the average number of functional units achieved during the use of the product

- U_{av} is the average number of functional units achieved during use of an industry-average product

Calculation of the MCI

The MCI^*_p can be calculated using the following formula:

$$MCI^*_p = 1 - LFI \cdot F(X) \tag{59}$$

Where $F(X)$ is a factor created as a function F of the utility X that specifies the effect of the product's utility on the MCI:

$$F(X) = \frac{0.9}{X} \tag{60}$$

To avoid that the MCI_p becomes negative, the MCI further defines as:

$$MCI_p = (0, MCI^*_p) \tag{61}$$

As most products consist of more than one material, parts or sub-assembly, the MCI can be constructed by summing over each individual material, part or sub-assembly.

3.10.2 Application of the MCI in the studies identified in the literature review

When it comes to applying the MCI for BbS, especially two parameters can be challenging to establish. Firstly, when a material can be considered a sustained production and secondly, how to define the utility function for biobased products. Therefore, the following review of the article applying the MCI will focus on these two specific aspects. The definition of sustained production is only relevant for the article using the updated method from 2019. An overview of the review is provided in Table 23.

Study	Product group	Utility function	Adaptations
MCI based on the original method from 2015			
(Razza et al., 2020)	Bio-based and biodegradable mulch films	Default value of 0.9 is used (unsure why)	The mass of the bio-based is used as the recycled material. The composting or biodegradation in soil is counted as recycled materials
(Stegmann et al., 2023)	Plastic polyethylene furanoate (PEF) and polyethylene terephthalate (PET) for 250 ml bottles	The cumulative material use intensity, and the length of the material's use is assessed separately. The cumulative material use intensity is the percentage of additional material use achieved based on the initial	The study is inspired by the MCI from 2015. However, only the utility function is included. Where the material use intensity and the length of the material use is assess separately.

		<p>virgin material.</p> <p>The material length is provided in carbon sequestration time</p>	
(Kusumo et al., 2022) (Rocchi et al., 2021)	Agricultural production (poultry industry)	<p>The MCI is not applied only listed</p> <p>The utility function is calculated as the complementary of the mortality rate, representing the percentage of animals staying for a hole cycle.</p>	<p>The study is based on a modified version of the MCI from 2015.</p> <p>The calculation of the virgin feedstock is based on the feed conversion ratio.</p> <p>Unrecoverable waste is calculated subtracting the parts going for composting and biogas recovery.</p>
(Escribà-Gelonch et al., 2023)	Nanofertilizer	<p>U is expressed as the intensity of parameters of plant growth and L as the bioavailability period.</p>	<p>The study is based on the MCI from 2015.</p> <p>LFI is keep constant for all processes of the nanofertilizers</p>
Studies based on the MCI Updated in 2019			
(Gallo et al., 2024)	Agri-food products (jam, flour, pasta, oil, mozzarella, chicken breast)	<p>The utility function is considered negligible as it is outside the system boundary of the case studies.</p>	<p>The study is based on the MCI from 2019.</p> <p>Organic products are in the study considered to be sustained production.</p>
(Karayılan et al., 2021)	Bio-based biodegradable plastic packaging	<p>Not specified details is provided.</p>	<p>The MCI is adapted to plastic value chains.</p>
(Wiedemann et al., 2022)	Textiles (renewable and non-renewable fibers)	<p>In the supplementary materials it seems as if Utility function is set to 1 for both materials. However, not specific details are provided on how the function is calculated.</p>	<p>From the supplementary material, it seems as if certified renewable feedstock is considered sustainable input. However, no details are provided.</p>
(Corona et al., 2022)	Lignin-based asphalt	<p>The average lifetime of roads is 30 years. The lifetime of lignin-based and the bitumen-based</p>	<p>It is assumed that lignin is produced from sustainable feedstock using a specific process</p>

	<p>scenarios varies from 12-15 for the top layer and 24 to 30 for the base layer.</p> <p>The utility of asphalt is represented as the average number of loading cycles before failure due to rutting or fatigue. It is presumed in the study that lignin-based and bitumen-based roads have similar performance.</p>	called the Goldilocks.
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Table 23: Overview of how the utility function is defined in the studies and other adaptations made included how Sustained production is defined

MCI used on Bio-based biodegradable plastic packaging value chains

The study by Karayilan et al. (2021) provides a prospective evaluation of circular economy practices within plastic packaging value chains. It considers three circular economy strategies: (1) advancing cross-sectoral valorization of plastic waste through industrial symbiosis, (2) improving recycling efficiency, and (3) the application of a new bio-based and biodegradable plastic product. The study applies the MCI from 2019 to the case of bio-based biodegradable plastic packaging. The study further adapts the MCI to plastic value chains, using the following formula:

$$\text{Overall MCI} = \frac{[(\text{MCI value of products}) \cdot (\text{Score of product})]}{\text{Total score of all products}} \quad (62)$$

Where the score of the products is based on an optional analysis covering the following criteria:

- Substitution rate for recycled plastic (%)
- GDP of the sector
- The demand for recycled plastic
- Service shelf life
- Biodegradability
- Energy demand during manufacturing
- Prevention of marine litter
- Degradation time in nature
- GWP of the product during manufacturing

The scores of the products were then used as a weighting factor

The MCI adaptation to nanofertilizer

The study by Escribá-Gelonch et al. (2023) applies the MCI to plant growth performance where different types of fertilizers are applied (three nanofertilizers and one biostimulant) and these were compared to two control groups (no-use of micronutrients and micronutrient supplied via conventional fertilizer). In the study, LFI is kept constant for all nanofertilizer processes. U is expressed as the intensity of parameters for plant growth

(covering physiological, pigmentation, photosynthetic-complex and metabolism activity performance). L is repressed as the bioavailability period.

The MCI adaptation to zootechnical products

The study by Rocchi et al. (2021) adapts the MCI from 2015 to zootechnical products more specifically poultry production. The modifications cover the calculation of virgin feedstock, unrecoverable waste and the utility function. The virgin feedstock is calculated based on the feed conversion ratio using the following equation:

$$V = \frac{M_f}{FCR} + Ma \quad (63)$$

Where:

- Ma is the initial mass of the animal
- Mf is the feed mass
- FCR is the feed conversion ratio

Unrecoverable waste (W_0) is calculated by subtracting the part used for composting and biogas recovery, using the following equation:

$$W_0 = W(1 - C_R - C_U) + M_A(1 - C_{RA} - C_{UA}) \quad (64)$$

Where:

- M_A is the mass of the manure
- C_{RA} and C_{UA} are the fraction of manure collected for recycling and reuse
- W is the share of the mass which is discharged
- C_R is the fraction of the product collected for recycling in this case biogas recovery
- C_U is the fraction of the product collected for reuse in this case composting

For the utility function (F(U)) is simplified and represented by the complement of the mortality rate. This represents the % of animals going through the life cycle.

Material Utility (MU)

The study by Stegmann et al. (2023) assesses the use of bio-based plastic polyethylene furanoate (PEF) and polyethylene terephthalate (PET) for 250 ml bottles over multiple mechanical (MR) and chemical (CR) recycling trips. The study assesses the GHG emissions and supplements the assessment with a material utility (MU) indicator. The indicator is adopted from the MCI 2015 indicator. It applies only the utility function of the MCI and assesses the cumulative material use intensity and the length of the material's use separately.

The cumulative material use intensity (MI) is calculated using the following equation:

$$MI_{i,k} = \frac{(\sum_{t=1}^n m_{k,i}(t-1) \cdot r_t)}{m_{k(t=0)}} \quad (65)$$

Where:

- k is the bottle types (PET or PEF)
- i is the waste management case (there are xx covering)
- $m_{k,i}$ is the weight in grammes of the bottle (t=0) or the remaining bottle material (t=1-15) per bottle type or waste management case (i)
- t is the number of recycling trips (1-15) where t=0 is the initial bottle production

- r_i is the recycling rate in % per waste management case
- m is the cumulatively recycled polymers
- n is the maximum number of recycling trips
- r is the recycling rate

The length of the material use is expressed in carbon sequestration time, and it is calculated using the following formula:

$$C_{k,i}(t) = CC_k \cdot m_{k,i}(t - 1) \cdot r_i \quad (66)$$

Where,

- C_k is the Carbon content per bottled type (k) in %

3.10.3 Sub-conclusion

Some of the cases where the MCI is applied to biobased products are biobased products that will, to some extent, enter the technical cycle. This includes the studies on plastic products by Razza et al. (2020) Stegmann et al. (2023), and Karayilan et al. (2021), which also cover the biodegradation of the plastic products. However, other end-of-life strategies are also assessed in these studies. Additionally, it includes the study by Corona et al. (2022) on lignin-based asphalt and the study by Wiedemann et al. on textiles. For these products entering the technical system, it can be easier to define the utility function, whereas it can be more difficult to define the length and intensity of use for perishable and biodegradable products.

However, the study by Stegmann et al. (2023) provided an interesting adaptation as it used the carbon sequestration time as a representation for the product's length of use. This way of expressing the durability is interesting to examine further and also links to task 2.1.

The remaining studies provided different adaptations of the utility function and the understanding of the length and intensity of the product in a purely biobased system. In the study by Rocchi et al. (2021) on the poultry industry, the utility function was expressed as the complement of the mortality rate, expressed as the percentage of animals staying for the whole cycle. In the study by Escribá-Gelonch et al. (2023), the utility was expressed as the intensity of selected parameters of plant growth and their bioavailability.

In the study by Gallo et al. (2024), the utility function of the product was considered negligible as it was considered outside of the system boundary. This understanding of setting a system boundary is a very solid approach in LCA. However, the argument can be contested in the context of the MCI, where the purpose is to provide a holistic circularity assessment of a product covering various CE strategies. So, in this specific adaptation of the MCI, only the linearity of the product is assessed.

In the study by Wiedemann et al. (2022), the utility function is set to 1 for both the renewable and non-renewable fibers, as it is assumed that the length and intensity of use are the same for the two products as the industry average.

These studies also provide valuable insight into how sustained production is assessed. In the study by Gallo et al. (2024), organic products are considered sustained production. In the study by Wiedemann et al. (2022) certified renewable feedstock is considered sustained production, and in the study by Corona et al. (2022), a specific patented process is considered sustained production.

Finally, the study by Karayilan et al. (2021) could potentially be interesting in the context of the LCA4BIO project as it provides an adaptation of the MCI indicator to provide a prospective evaluation of an entire value chain.

In conclusion, there is a broad interpretation of how the utility function can be expressed for biobased systems depending on the product system under consideration. Some of the studies also made use of simplifications, such as considering the utility outside the system boundary and assuming the same utility as an industry

average. This, of course, compromises the holistic nature of the MCI. The way of categorizing sustained production also varies considerably among the studies, and little guidance is provided both in the identified applications and in the MCI method.

3.11 The use of LCA indicators to assess or supplement circularity assessments - coordination with task 2.3

In the following Table 24 references that applying circular indicators for LCA of biobased products are reviewed with focus on the sectors they cover, system boundaries, LCA models and reference models and the indicators applied.

Reference	Sector	System boundaries	LCA models	Reference models	Indicators applied(impact categories)
(Hoehn et al., 2019)	Eggs, Meat, Fish and seafood, Dairy, Cereals, Sweets, Pulses Vegetable oils, Vegetables, Fruits, Roots	Agricultural production, processing and packaging, distribution and consumption, “cradle to consumer”	An empirical index so-called EROI _{ce} , is proposed, which quantifies the amount of nutritional energy that is recovered from the FL of each category of food under study, based on its treatment in three different scenarios: (i) landfill with biogas recovery (L), (ii) incineration with energy recovery (I) and (iii) anaerobic digestion and composting (AD&C).	ISO 14040 ISO 14044	The daily intake of food category for a 11,493 kJ per capita per day diet The primary energy invested in producing the food.
(Lokesh et al., 2020)	Packaging (2 packaging films)	Gate-to-gate environmental LCA	Comparative gate-to-gate LCA of packaging film. Using hybridized sustainability	EU-PEF guidance on product sustainability evaluation	Hazardous chemical use, Feedstock intensity (FI) and circular-process

			metrics for use in life cycle assessment of bio-based products: resource efficiency and circularity. Derived from principles of green chemistry.		feedstock intensity. Waste factor (WF) and circular-process waste factor (CPWF) Product renewability (PR) Process material circularity (PMC) Energy intensity (EI) and circular-process energy intensity (CPEI)
(Karayılan et al., 20219	Plastic packaging value chain	All stages from collection of plastic packaging wastes to their EoL management to valorization in packaging, automotive, agriculture, fibers, construction and EEE industries	The level of circularity is represented by MCI. In the MCI optimization model, the material circularity of products, which are manufactured with the contribution of recycled plastic, is investigated.	Not specified but follows ISO 14040	MCI (Also summarized for value chain) Climate change (CO ₂) Marine Ecotoxicity (t 1,4-DB eq/ kiloton plastic packaging waste)
(Stanchev et al., 2020)	The anaerobic treatment of dairy processing	3 levels - Plant - Processing Value chain (Crop to digestion)	Conventional LCA - Goal and scope definition	ISO 14040, 2006	LCA: Climate change Ozone depletion Freshwater

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Life cycle inventory (LCI), - Life cycle impact assessment and - Interpretation of results <p>The results of the LCA identify the processes that have the highest impact in the product lifecycle and facilitate the selection of suitable measures for the overall environmental impact reduction</p> <p>The avoided impacts from the substitution of mineral fertilisers with the organic fertiliser were calculated based on the IPCC guidelines (IPCC, 2006)</p> <p>A. The waste management system for small plastic bottles in the Netherlands until 2021, based on post-separation, source-separation, MR and incineration with energy recovery (ER).</p> <p>B. A waste</p>	<p>ISO 14040 and 14044</p> <p>IPCC 2013 GWP100a</p>	<p>eutrophication</p> <p>Ionising radiation</p> <p>Agricultural land occupation ALO</p> <p>Water depletion</p> <p>Metal depletion</p> <p>Fossil depletion</p> <p>To supplement traditional LCA:</p> <p>Material circularity performance indicator (MCPI)</p> <p>Environmental circularity performance indicator (ECPI)</p> <p>GWP (Global Warming Potential)</p>
<p>(Stegmann et al., 2023)</p>	<p>Waste management system for plastic bottles.</p>	<p>Cradle-to-grave with a strong focus on EoL</p>			

(Yilan et al., 2023)	Bio-based and biodegradable plastics.	All stages from raw material production to EoL treatment.	<p>collection predominantly based on a deposit system combined with MR and ER.</p> <p>C. A waste collection predominantly based on a deposit system combined with CR and ER.</p> <p>D. A non-circular scenario, assuming the complete incineration of the bottles with energy recovery.</p>	<p>EU taxonomy criteria combined with LCA based KPI's</p> <p>Environmental Footprint 3.0 method</p>	<p>Traditional environmental indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Climate change Emission of particulate matter Photochemical ozone formation Acidification Freshwater eutrophication Direct land use Net deforestation balance <p>Supplemented with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Depletion of fossil fuels
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			for both BB and FB mulch films. However, removal of film, transportation and End-of-Life (EoL) treatment stages are considered only for the FB mulch film. Three EoL scenarios for FB mulch films are considered, being incineration, landfill, and recycling.		[MJ]. Depletion of non-renewable primary materials expressed as mass or abiotic depletion potential (CE2(b)) Production of non-recyclable waste Water scarcity footprint
(Wiedeman et al., 2022)	Textiles	Cradle to grave	An attributional life cycle assessment (aLCA) approach was used to assess the environmental impacts of wearing a sweater made from PET-f or PET-b fibre. The method used was consistent with ISO LCA standards.	Attributional LCA ISO14040 ecoinvent v3.6 'attributional' database	Material Circularity Indicator (MCI) The World Business Council for Sustainable Development % circularity indicator The Circular Materials Guidelines (CMG) feedstock content requirements The Cradle to Cradle Certified™ Product Standard Material Reutilization Score (MRS).
(Gallo et al.,	Agri Food	Cradle to grave: From the procurement of raw	MCI-LCA methodological	ISO 14040-	Traditional LCA

2024)	products	materials and packaging, the transport of raw materials and the production of agri-food products, to their distribution, and the end of life of packaging and waste, with the exclusion of the use phase.	integration model. Comparative case studies were selected in the agri-food sector since their products encompass both biological and technical materials.	14044	indicators supplemented with MCI.
(Corona et al., 2022)	Lignin-based asphalt	Life cycle perspective (from the extraction of raw materials to the disposal of the road) and different sets of metrics.	LCA method integrating 3 circular indicators (MCI, BCS100 and C-BSC)	Not specified (follows ISO 14040-14044)	Traditional LCA indicators supplemented with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MCI - The BCS100 indicator measures the total amount of biogenic carbon stored over a period of 100 years C-BCS accounts for the share of carbon content that is circular, e.g., recycled or reused, after one recycling cycle

Table 24: Overview of the studies applying LCA

3.11.1 System boundaries

System boundaries for the LCA of biobased systems vary across the references. For food products, it includes agricultural production, processing and packaging, distribution, and consumption, following a "cradle-to-consumer" approach. In contrast, the analysis of packaging films adopts a gate-to-gate perspective, focusing

on environmental impacts within specific stages of production.

The plastic packaging value chain includes all stages from the collection of plastic packaging waste to its end-of-life (EoL) management. Similarly, the system boundary for the anaerobic treatment of dairy processing waste includes three levels: the plant level, the processing level, and the value chain, extending from crop cultivation to digestion.

Waste management for plastic bottles follows a cradle-to-grave approach, with a strong emphasis on EoL processes. Textiles and agri-food products also use a cradle-to-grave framework. For textiles, this includes all life cycle stages, while for agri-food products, it covers raw material procurement, packaging, transport, production, distribution, and EoL for packaging and waste, excluding the use phase. Lignin-based asphalt adopts a life cycle perspective, analyzing impacts from raw material extraction to road disposal.

3.11.2 Indicators applied:

In the LCA of biobased systems, a mix of traditional environmental indicators and circularity-specific metrics is applied to evaluate sustainability. Commonly used traditional indicators include climate change (CO₂ emissions), global warming potential (GWP), and resource depletion (fossil, water, and metals), supplemented by metrics such as eutrophication, acidification, and land use impacts.

Circularity indicators focus on material and process efficiency, with widespread use of the Material Circularity Indicator (MCI) and Product Renewability (PR). Energy and material flows are assessed using feedstock intensity (FI), waste factor (WF), and their circular-process variants. Metrics for biogen carbon are also applied in metrics like biogenic carbon storage (BCS100) and Circular Biogenic Carbon Share (C-BCS).

While traditional indicators dominate due to their standardized nature, circularity-specific metrics such as MCI, Environmental Circularity Performance Indicator (ECPI), and Material Circularity Performance Indicator (MCPI) are often added to assess circularity and thereby integrate circular economy principles into LCA frameworks.

4 RESULTS OF THE UNSTRUCTURED REVIEW

As part of the task description, task 2.2 should be coordinated with the work of the Calimero project and the Orienting project. Therefore, the main results when it comes to circularity indicators are accounted for in this section.

4.1 ISO 59000 series of standards

In 2024, the 59000 family of standards was published. The idea behind these standards is to harmonise the understanding of the circular economy and assist its implementation and measurement (ISO, 2024a)(ISO, 2024a). The ISO 59000 family of standards covers five standards that support each other:

- ISO 59004: Circular economy – Vocabulary, principles, and guidance for implementation
- ISO 59010: Circular economy – Guidance on the transition of business models and value networks
- ISO 59014: Environmental management and circular economy – Sustainability and traceability of the recovery of secondary materials – Principles and requirements
- ISO 59020: Circular economy – Measuring and assessing circularity performance
- ISO 59040: Circular economy – Product circularity data sheet

The following section will provide a short introduction to the standards and then go into more detail with ISO 59020, focusing on measuring and assessing circularity performance.

The ISO 59000 series of standards provides its own definition of a circular economy, which is an “economic system that uses a systemic approach to maintain a circular flow of resources, by recovering, retaining, or adding to their value, while contributing to sustainable development” (ISO, 2024a, p. 1)(ISO, 2024a, p. 1). Thus, the standard family contributes to the diversity of circular economy definitions existing in both academic and non-academic literature.

4.1.1 The ISO 59004: circular economy – Vocabulary, principles and guidance for implementation

The ISO 59004 provides a definition of what a circular economy is, covering vision, principles, and guidance for how to implement a circular economy in an organisation (ISO, 2024b)(ISO, 2024b). The ISO 59004 proclaims that “The long-term vision of a circular economy is, by design, to provide appropriate solutions for the reduced efficient and effective use of resources, and to prevent harmful releases, losses, and environmental degradation when meeting societal needs”.

Furthermore, the ISO 59004 introduces six principles that an organisation should follow to transition to a circular economy. These cover:

- **System thinking** – This implies that the organisation should take a life cycle perspective and apply a long-term perspective in relation to their social and environmental impacts.
- **Value creation** – This implies that organisations should provide effective solutions which can recover, retain, or add value, contributing to environmental and socio-economic value where resources are used efficiently.
- **Value sharing** – This strategy covers that organisations should collaborate with interested parties in their value chain or in value networks to create value to benefit society.
- **Resource stewardship** – This strategy implies that organisations should manage flows and stock in a sustainable manner by closing, slowing, and narrowing resource flows.
- **Resource traceability** – This strategy implies that organisations should collect and maintain data which enables them to track resources through their value chain and share this data with interested parties.

- **Ecosystem resilience** – This strategy urges organisations to develop and implement practices and strategies focused on resilience and regeneration of ecosystems and their biodiversity.

The ISO 59004 also provides an outline of considerations for adopting the principles, such as design and development, collaboration for management of information and resources, risk and opportunity management, the relationship between value creation and resource use, and awareness of stocks and flows. Along with actions that contribute to a circular economy in accordance with the outlined principles. Finally, the standard outlines implementation guidance following four steps in a continuous circle in line with the plan, do, check, act approach. Covering circular economy purpose, mission, vision, and goals definition, circular economy strategic priorities and action plan development, circular economy implementation, and circular economy monitoring, reviewing, and reporting. Furthermore, it emphasises an assessment of the importance of the context and reference situation.

4.1.2 ISO 59010 Circular economy – Guidance on the transition of business models and value networks

The ISO 59010 provides more business-oriented guidance on how to move towards circular business models and value networks (ISO, 2024a)(ISO, 2024a). The standard covers aspects such as:

- How to set the goals and boundaries
- How to determine the circular economy strategy
- How to transition the value creation model of an organisation or a value network towards circularity
- How to review and monitor continuous improvement

An interesting contribution of ISO 59010 is the understanding of a value chain network and the relevant actors for transitioning to a circular economy.

4.1.3 ISO 59014 Environmental management and circular economy – Sustainability and traceability of the recovery of secondary materials – Principles, requirements and guidance

The ISO 59014 aligns with both the 59000 series of standards and the ISO 14000 series of standards (ISO, 2024c)(ISO, 2024c). The standard focuses specifically on the recovery of secondary materials. It specifies principles, requirements, and guidance for organisations on how they can ensure traceability and sustainability of activities and processes related to the recovery of secondary materials.

4.1.4 ISO 59020 Circular economy – Measuring and assessing circularity performance

The ISO 59020 provides a framework on how to measure and assess circularity performance and sustainability impacts (ISO, 2024d)(ISO, 2024d). A number of steps are proposed when assessing the circularity of organisations:

Firstly, the context of the application should be determined. This covers the circular goals and actions defined in accordance with ISO 59004, ISO 59010, or ISO 59014. This should answer questions such as: which system level is in focus, which circular goals are relevant, which circularity aspects should be considered, which social, economic, or environmental issues should be considered, and what the purpose of the circularity assessment is.

ISO 59020 provides a set of core circularity indicators that should be considered when carrying out a circularity assessment and measurement, along with a set of additional circularity indicators to supplement the core indicators in accordance with the goal setting of the assessment.

Then the standard proposes three stages:

- **Stage 1 - Boundary setting:** This stage includes activities such as defining the system in focus along with its exchanges with the social, environmental, and economic systems, stakeholders and value network actors, and data quality requirements.

- **Stage 2 – Circularity measurement and data acquisition:** This stage covers four steps: (1) choose circularity indicators, (2) identify information to be measured, (3) acquire data, and (4) calculate and/or aggregate.
- **Stage 3 – Circularity assessment and reporting:** This stage covers an evaluation of the results of the circularity assessment along with reporting of the results.

In addition to the framework for the circularity assessment, ISO 59020 provides a number of core indicators and additional indicators to use in the circularity assessment. The core indicators are categorised according to five categories: resource inflows, resource outflows, energy, water, and economy (Table 25). Furthermore, the indicators are either classified as mandatory or optional, where all energy, water, and economy indicators are classified as optional. The indicators are all simple indicators covering one circularity strategy.

Indicators	Category	Description	Mandatory or optional
Average reuse content of an inflow	Resource inflows	Part of input material resources which are reuse products or component.	Mandatory
Average recycled content of and inflow	Resource inflows	Part of the input materials which is recycled material	Mandatory
Average renewable content of an inflow	Resource inflows	Part of the inflow of material resources which is sustainably produced renewable material	Mandatory
Average lifetime of product or material relative to industry average	Resource outflows	It is an indicator representing the time a product or material will stay in use compared to an industry average	Optional
Percent actual reused product and component derived from outflow	Resource outflow	Part of the outflow of the material that is reused	Mandatory
Percent actual recycled material derived from outflow	Resource outflow	Part of the outflow that ends up as recycled material	Mandatory
Percent actual recirculation of outflow in the biological cycle	Resource outflow	Part of the outflow which is recirculated at the end-of-life and returned safely to the biosphere meeting the qualifying condition for recirculation	Mandatory
Average percent of energy consumed that	Energy	Part of the new consumed energy which is considered renewable	Optional

is renewable energy		energy considering both energy inflows and outflows	
Percent water withdrawal from inflow circular sources	Water	Percent of annual water demand coming from circular sources	Optional
Percent waste discharged in accordance with quality requirements	Water	Percent by volume of the water withdrawn which is discharged in accordance with circularity principles	Optional
Ration (on-site or internal) water reuse or recirculation	Water	Reuse cycles of on-site water	Optional
Material productivity	Economic	Ration between the revenue generation and the total mass of all linear resource inflows	Optional
Resource intensity index	Economic	A measure of the economic growth versus total resource use	Optional

Table 25: Overview of the core circularity indicators covered by the ISO 59020 (ISO, 2024d, pp. 17–18) (ISO, 2024d, pp. 17–18)

The ISO 59020 also provides a number of additional indicators which can be used to supplement the core indicators. These indicators are either emerging circularity indicators, indicators targeting specific aspects, or indicators not directly focused on circularity but still relevant for circularity. The indicators are listed in Table 26.

	Category	Description
Percent designed reusability rate of the outflow	Resource outflow	Design-based reusability
Percent design recyclability rate of the outflow	Resource outflow	Design-based recyclability
Percent energy recovered from residual, non-renewable and non-recoverable resource outflows	Energy	The energy recovered from residual, non-renewable resource outflow divided by the total energy inflow (in percent)
Energy intensity	Energy	Is the ratio between the total energy inflow and the number of units produced during the reference time
Nutrients extraction	Water	Is the amount of nutrient extracted from the water

from discharged water		before the water is discharged
Water intensity	Water	The ratio between the total inflow of water and the units produced during the reference time
Net value added	Economic	The value of a products deducted the negative economic cost factors
Value per mass	Economic	The ratio between the product revenue value in monetary units and the total mass of resource in weight
Resource productivity	Economic	The ratio between the GDP in monetary units and the sum of negative impact costs in monetary units
Genuine process indicator	Economic	The GDP, DMC or RMC in monetary units deducted the sum of negative impact cost in monetary units

Table 26: Overview of the additional indicators provided in annex B (ISO, 2024d, p. 46)(ISO, 2024d, p. 46)

4.1.5 ISO 59040: Circular economy – Product circularity data sheet

The ISO 59040 introduces the product circularity data sheet, which is intended to enable circular business models by providing the framework for the exchange of relevant circularity data (ISO, 2024e). The ISO 59040 provides a general methodology for a product circularity data sheet, covering aspects such as implementation, operation, monitoring, reviewing, and maintenance. It provides specific requirements for the information to report on when creating a product circularity data sheet template and assistance on how to manage and share a product circularity data sheet. It also contains recommendations and requirements on how to exchange information supporting a circular economy when using a product circularity data sheet.

4.2 ORIENTING

ORIENTING (Operational Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment Methodology Supporting Decisions Towards a Circular Economy) was a research project running from 2020 to 2023. The purpose of the project was to “develop an operational methodology for product Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment” by including a life cycle approach that includes an analysis of the environmental, social, and economic impacts (ORIENTING, 2024). One of the deliverables of the project was a critical evaluation of material criticality and product-related circularity approaches (Bachmann et al., 2021).

Especially, the part about the product-related circularity approaches is relevant for task 2.2, and, therefore, a short introduction is provided here. The specific goals of the deliverable on product-related circularity were:

1. The identification of approaches, concepts, methods, and indicators relevant for product circularity, which could be integrated into ORIENTING’s LCA framework
2. Carry out a critical evaluation of the most promising indicators to use in LCSA
3. Provide recommendations for methodological developments

Based on a systematic literature review and several selection criteria, nine formulas and indicators were identified as the most relevant circularity metrics. The metrics are presented in Table 27. The indicators were scored in relation to stakeholder acceptance, credibility and suitability, applicability/complexity, transparency, scientific robustness, completeness, and compatibility with the life-cycle approach. Overall, the MCI scored the highest (A), followed by the PLCM, longevity, CFF, PCI, and UOR/FRS (-A). However, a limitation of ORIENTING is that it did not have a specific focus on bio-based systems, and it also covers product-related indicators (micro level), whereas LCA4BIO covers both micro and macro level indicators.

	Short description	Format	Reference
Product-level circularity Metric (PLCM, C-metric)	Ratio between the economic value of recirculated parts and the economic value of all parts	Single score indicator	(Linder et al., 2017)
Material Circularity Indicator (MCI)	Measures the extent to which linear flows are minimised and restorative flows are maximised and how intensively and long the materials are used compared to an industry-average	Single score Indicator	(Godiin et al., n.d.)
Longevity indicator	Measures the material retention based on the time a resource is in use in a product-system.	Indicator	(Franklin-Johnson et al., 2016)
Circular Footprint Formula (CFF)	The formula is used to assess the end-of-life in an LCA and as a way to allocate burdens and credits between suppliers and users.	Formular	(Luca Zampori and Rana Pant, 2019)
Product circularity indicator (PCI)	Further development of the MCI	Single score Indicator	
Circularity index (Circ(T))	It is a performance indicator for the circularity of a material	Single score indicator	(Pauliuk, 2018)
Value-based resource efficiency (VRE)	Covers resource efficiency and circularity in terms of the market value of the scarce resources	Single score indicator	(Di Maio et al., 2017)
Sustainable Circular Index (SCI)	The indicator is based on a five-phase framework to calculate the index covering indicator selection, weighting (delphi-based), normalisation, aggregation and index construction. Covers other aspects than circularity.	Index	(Azevedo et al., 2017)
In-use occupation-based indicators	Covers two indicators, the in-use occupation ratio (UOR) and final retention in society (FRS). The UOR is	Two indicators	(Moraga et al., 2021)

the ratio (in percentage) between the in-use occupation along the product cycle and theoretical in-use occupation. FRS is the residual percentage of the virgin raw material at year 25.

Table 27: Circularity approaches covered by the ORIENTING project (Bachmann et al., 2021)

4.3 CALIMERO project

The industry case studies analysis to improve environmental performance and sustainability of Bio-Based industrial processes (CALIMERO) is a European project running from July 2022 to July 2025. The goal of the project is to create a common framework for LCA methodologies for certain biobased sectors such as construction, woodworking, textile, pulp & paper and biochemicals. The outset of the project is the PEF indicators, but additional indicators are also proposed. The project also focuses on circularity in deliverable 1.3 and deliverable 3.2. In deliverable 1.3, it identifies challenges related to the modelling of circularity and in D3.2 it investigates the integration of circular economy and criticality aspects in the LCSA framework.

Deliverable 1.3 identifies three key challenges in modelling circularity related to the bioeconomy, covering:

- The modelling of dynamic carbon footprint and allocation of biogenic carbon capture credits when dealing with successive product systems
- The combination of circularity indicators with LCSA decision support when striving to optimise bioeconomy cycles and dealing with competing needs.
- The modelling of complex cascading chains of biomaterials

Furthermore, for assessing the performance of circularity, it is recommended to use the indicators identified by the ORIENTING project or by the evaluation of Luthin et al. (2023). The two studies recommend the use of either the MCI, PCI, PLCM, longevity indicators, UOR and FRS.

In deliverable 3.2, the three key challenges were approached more specifically: the study looks into the modelling of multifunctionality in connection with different circular strategies, as this is a key challenge. The study examines three approaches partitioning, substitution and system expansion and apply these to a case study of cellulose insulation. More specifically, three normative LCA standards are covered: the product environmental footprint, the EN 15804+A2:2019 and Allocation of the point of substitution. Along with a consequential LCA and a system/process-based LCA and two complementary CE indicators (MCI and CTI). The study provides a review of CE strategies and examines to which extent these strategies are covered by the different approaches for modelling multifunctionality and the complementary circular economy indicators (MCI and CTI). The study showed that consequential LCA is the most comprehensive LCA method to model CE strategies, as it covered 42 strategies, followed by the PEF guide. Whereas the use of system expansion from a recycler's perspective covers only 13 strategies and is the least comprehensive approach. The study also provides a review of circularity strategies in S-LCA and LCC/ economic LCA. The review concludes that there are few papers that integrates social and economic performance when considering circularity. Therefore, future studies should approach this issue along with how to identify social and economic hotspots within circularity strategies.

The industry case studies analysis to improve environmental performance and sustainability of bio-based industrial processes (CALIMERO) is a European project running from July 2022 to July 2025. The goal of the

project is to create a common framework for LCA methodologies for certain bio-based sectors such as construction, woodworking, textiles, pulp & paper, and biochemicals. The project initially focuses on PEF indicators but also proposes additional indicators. It addresses circularity in deliverables 1.3 (Schaubroeck et al., 2024) and 3.3 (Schrijvers et al., 2024). Deliverable 1.3 identifies challenges related to the modeling of circularity, while deliverable 3.3 investigates the integration of circular economy and criticality aspects into the LCSEA framework.

Deliverable 1.3 highlights three key challenges in modelling circularity within the bioeconomy:

- The modelling of dynamic carbon footprints and the allocation of biogenic carbon capture credits when dealing with successive product systems.
- The combination of circularity indicators with LCSEA decision support to optimize bioeconomy cycles while addressing competing needs.
- The modelling of complex cascading chains of biomaterials.

For assessing circularity performance, it is recommended to use indicators identified by the ORIENTING project (Bachmann et al., 2021) or the evaluation by Luthin et al. (2024). These studies suggest using indicators such as MCI, PCI, PLCM, longevity indicators, UOR, and FRS.

Deliverable 3.2 approaches the three key challenges more specifically, examining the modeling of multifunctionality in connection with different circular strategies. The study explores three approaches—partitioning, substitution, and system expansion—and applies them to a case study of cellulose insulation. It covers three normative LCA standards: the product environmental footprint, EN 15804+A2:2019, and allocation at the point of substitution, along with consequential LCA, system/process-based LCA, and two complementary CE indicators (MCI and CTI). The study reviews CE strategies and assesses the extent to which these strategies are covered by different approaches for modelling multifunctionality and complementary circular economy indicators.

The study found that consequential LCA is the most comprehensive method for modelling CE strategies, covering 42 strategies, followed by the PEF guide. In contrast, system expansion from a recycler's perspective covers only 13 strategies and is the least comprehensive approach. The study also reviews circularity strategies in S-LCA and LCC/economic LCA, concluding that few papers integrate social and economic performance when considering circularity. Therefore, future studies should address this issue and identify social and economic hotspots within circularity strategies.

5 SELECTION OF INDICATOR SETS AND GUIDANCE DOCUMENT FOR SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT OF CIRCULAR BIO-BASED STRATEGIES

The following section covers a selection of three indicator sets: two generic indicator sets at the micro and macro levels, and one for the wood sector covering the meso and macro levels (Sections 6.1–6.3). A generic indicator set at the meso level was not developed, as only six indicators were identified at this level. The three indicator sets form the basis for the guidance document for sustainability assessment of circular bio-based strategies which is presented in section 6.4. The selection was based on the scoring of the indicators in Appendices 2 and 3.

5.1 Generic indicator-set on micro-level

5.1.1 Reduce reliance on fossil resources

A total of six micro-level indicators were identified that support the circularity strategy of reducing reliance on fossil resources, each scoring between 1 and 2 (see Appendix 2). Among these, the two highest-scoring indicators were product renewability and circular-process energy intensity (CPEI). These indicators reflect two distinct yet complementary aspects of the strategy: the shift toward bio-based feedstocks and the efficient use of energy. As a result, both indicators are incorporated into the sustainability guideline. Additionally, energy intensity is included as it is the recommended indicator in the ISO 59020 standard.

5.1.2 Use resource efficiently including use of residues and wastes

A total of eleven micro-level indicators were identified to support the circularity strategy of using resources efficiently, including the utilization of residues and waste. These indicators received scores ranging from -1 to 5 (see Appendix 2). The highest-scoring indicator was the Circular-Process Feedstock Intensity (CPFI), developed by Lokesh et al. (2020). This indicator primarily addresses resource efficiency by accounting not only for the main product but also for co-products, as well as recycled and recovered materials.

Two indicators specifically focused on waste: the Waste Factor and the Circular-Process Waste Factor (CPWF). Among these, the CPWF scored higher in terms of completeness, as it includes recycled and recovered materials in its assessment. Based on these evaluations, the selected indicators for this strategy are CPFI and CPWF.

5.1.3 Ensure generation of natural systems

For this circularity strategy, only two indicators were identified: Biogenic Carbon Storage over 100 years (BCS100) and Cumulative Biogenic Carbon Storage (cBCS) (see appendix 2). Both indicators specifically address the sub-strategy of maintaining carbon cycles. This highlights a significant gap—there is a clear need for further research and development to create micro-level indicators that target the broader goal of regenerating natural systems.

Both indicators received the same score (3). However, cBCS may be more compatible with Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodologies, as it tracks carbon storage over the actual lifespan of the product rather than a fixed 100-year period. Consequently, cBCS was selected for inclusion in the indicator set.

5.1.4 Recirculate

Indicators associated with the circularity strategy *recirculate* were among the most represented, with a total of eleven identified. Among these, the WBC circularity indicators and the Material Circularity Indicator (MCI, 2015) received the highest scores within this strategy. Ultimately, the MCI was selected due to its widespread application and its endorsement in both the CALIMERO and ORIENTING projects.

The MCI serves as a comprehensive indicator for assessing overall performance within the recirculate strategy. However, in certain cases, it may be necessary to evaluate specific sub-strategies such as recycling, reuse, and longevity/durability. As a result, additional indicators were selected to address these dimensions.

For longevity, the utility function of the MCI was employed in several of the reviewed studies—either in its original form or in an adapted version where the duration of material use was expressed in terms of carbon sequestration time. This adaptation is particularly relevant for products that remain in the biological cycle rather than entering the technical cycle. The utility function also aligns with ISO 59020 circularity indicator on average lifetime of product or material relative to industry average.

For products that do enter the technical cycle, indicators from the ISO 59020 standard can be applied to assess recycling and reuse, covering both material inflows and outflows. These indicators were selected as the indicators from the literature review did not score very high.

5.1.5 Extend the high-quality use - including cascading

Only one indicator—the Bioresource Utilization Index—was identified as covering the strategy of extending high-quality use, including cascading. However, this indicator received a relatively low score (-1), highlighting a clear need for further research and development of indicators and methodologies to effectively assess this circularity strategy.

5.1.6 Positive effect on economic viability

At the micro level, only three indicators were identified as addressing economic aspects, and these primarily focused on costs rather than overall economic viability. The highest-scoring method was Life Cycle Costing (score: 4), which is therefore recommended for assessing the economic dimension of circularity within sustainability assessment. However, this method is quite generic and not specifically tailored to circularity.

For this reason, it is advisable to supplement it with indicators that more directly target economic aspects of circularity, such as Material Productivity and the Resource Intensity Index, both of which are included in the ISO 59020 standard.

5.1.7 Positive effect on social equality

Only one method/ indicator the SLCC was identified covering the circularity strategy on positive effect on social equality and this scored quite low (-4). Consequently, no indicators are recommended for this strategy. Instead, more research is needed to provide applicable indicators to also cover this strategy.

5.1.8 Complex indicators

Five complex indicators were identified, meaning indicators targeting more than one of the circularity strategies. This complex indicator with the highest score was the MCI updated in 2019 (6). This indicator covers, in addition to the recirculate strategy, also sustainable sourcing of biological materials, and that the biological materials are uncontaminated and biologically available. This also implies that the indicator does not cover all the identified circularity strategies.

CE strategy	CE sub-strategy	Indicator
Reduce reliance on fossil resources	Energy efficiency	Energy intensity (EI)
	Energy efficiency	Circular-Process Energy Intensity (CPEI)
	Renewability	Product renewability (PR)
Resource efficiency including use of residues and wastes	Resource efficiency	Circular-process feedstock intensity (CPFI)
	Reduce waste	Circular-process waste factor (CPWF)
Regenerate	Maintain carbon cycles	Biogenic carbon storage (cBCS)

Recirculate	Generic	Material Circularity Indicator (MCI)
	Durability	Utility function of the MCI or average lifetime of a product material relative to industry average
	Reuse	Average reuse content of an inflow
	Reuse	Percent actual reused product and component derived from outflow
	Reuse	Percent designed reusability rate of the outflow
	Recycle	Average recycle content of an inflow
	Recycle	Percent actual recycled product and component derived from outflow
	Recycle	Percent design recyclability rate of the outflow
	Recirculation	Percent actual recirculation of outflow in the biological cycle
Extend the high-quality use including cascading		Bioresource utilization index
Positive effect on economic viability		Life Cycle Cost (LCC) Material productivity Resource intensity index
Positive effect on social equality		No indicator recommended
Complex indicators		Material Circularity Indicator (MCI) updated in 2019

Table 28: Overview of the indicator set on micro level

5.2 Generic Indicator Set on Macro Level

5.2.1 Reduce reliance on fossil resources

At the macro level, only three indicators were identified as addressing the circularity strategy of reducing reliance on fossil resources. These indicators received low scores, ranging from -5 to 0. Moreover, they focused exclusively on energy use and did not account for other types of renewable resources.

As a result, it is recommended to apply the ISO 59020 indicators related to both energy and the use of renewable resources to ensure a more comprehensive assessment of this circularity strategy.

5.2.2 Use resources efficiently including residues and wastes

For the circularity strategy use resources efficiently, including residues and waste, a total of 13 indicators and methods were identified. This represents a relatively well-developed area in terms of both the diversity of indicators and their scoring, which ranged from -3 to 5. The highest-scoring method was Material Flow Analysis (MFA). However, since MFA is considered a methodological framework rather than a standalone indicator, it was not included in the final indicator set. Among the indicators specifically addressing efficient resource use, Domestic Material Consumption (DMC) and Resource Productivity received the highest scores and are therefore included in the indicator set. For indicators focusing on waste, the two highest-scoring were Waste per DMC and Waste per GDP. These are also included in the indicator set to ensure adequate coverage of waste-related aspects.

5.2.3 Ensure regeneration of natural systems

For the circularity strategy *ensure regeneration of natural systems* at the macro level, 12 indicators were identified (see Appendix X). This reflects a diverse field of indicators, though most received relatively low scores, ranging from -8 to 0. This suggests a lower level of maturity and limited potential for immediate integration into harmonized Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) frameworks.

The three highest-scoring indicators were Biocapacity and Ecological Footprint (for both consumption and production). As a result, these are recommended for inclusion in the indicator set. All three are considered generic indicators.

Indicators targeting the sub-strategy *maintain nutrient cycles* scored poorly, with values ranging from -4 to -8. Additionally, no indicators addressing the maintenance of carbon cycles were identified at the macro level. This highlights a clear need for further research and development of indicators for this circularity strategy.

In particular, it may be valuable to explore the further development of indicators such as the Nutrient Circularity Indicator to better address the goal of maintaining nutrient cycles.

5.2.4 Recirculate

At the macro level, only five indicators were identified for the circularity strategy *recirculate*, and all of them focused exclusively on recycling. Aspects such as reuse and durability—also essential components of the recirculate strategy—were not covered by the identified indicators.

The two highest-scoring indicators were the Circular Material Use Rate (CMU) and Recycling Rates, and these are therefore included in the indicator set.

However, to ensure broader coverage of the recirculate strategy, it is recommended to supplement these with additional indicators from the ISO 59020 standard, which address other relevant aspects such as reuse and product durability.

5.2.5 Extend the high-quality use including cascading

At the macro level, the only identified indicator targeting the circularity strategy *extend high-quality use, including cascading* was composting. However, composting addresses only a small fraction of what is required to comprehensively assess this strategy. As a result, it is not currently possible to propose suitable indicators for this strategy within the indicator set. Furthermore, the ISO 59020 standard does not include indicators relevant to this circularity strategy, making supplementation from that source unfeasible. This highlights a clear need for further research and development of indicators specifically tailored to this area.

5.2.6 Positive Effect on Economic Viability

Only two indicators—environmental tax and revenues as a percentage of GDP, and patents—were identified as targeting the positive effect on economic viability at the macro level. Both received relatively low scores (-3). These indicators cover only a limited portion of what is relevant for assessing this strategy. Consequently, it is

recommended to apply indicators from the ISO 59020 standard that relate to economic aspects, specifically Material Productivity and the Resource Intensity Index.

5.2.7 Positive Effect on Social Equality

Only one indicator was identified as targeting the positive effect on social equality: the Social Progress Index (SPI). The SPI measures societal well-being based on social and environmental needs but does not link directly to specific circular activities. As such, it may be difficult to use for assessing the positive social impact of a particular circular initiative. Additionally, the SPI is challenging to harmonize with Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodologies. Therefore, no indicator is currently recommended for this strategy.

5.2.8 Complex Indicators

Three complex indicators were identified at the macro level: CE Eco-Innovation Index, Evaluation Index System for Circular Economy Development and Green Growth Indicators developed by the OECD. These are systems of indicators composed of multiple individual metrics. Among them, the OECD Green Growth Indicators received the highest score (-1), while the other two scored lower (-5). However, the OECD set is designed to assess green growth broadly and is not specifically tailored to circularity. This makes it difficult to extract relevant indicators for circular economy assessments without further refinement. As a result, no complex indicators are currently recommended at the macro level. Instead, further research is advised to develop or adapt complex indicator systems specifically for circularity.

CE Strategy	CE-Substrategy	Indicator
Reduce reliance on fossil resource	Renewability	Average percent of energy consumed that is renewable energy
	Renewability	Average renewable content of an inflow
	Energy	Percent energy recovered from residual, non-renewable and non-recoverable resource outflows
	Energy	Energy intensity
Use resource efficiency including residues and waste	Resource efficiency	Domestic material consumption
	Resource efficiency	Resource productivity
	Waste	Waste (DMC)
	Waste	Waste (GDP)
Ensure regeneration of natural systems	Generic	Biocapacity
	Generic	Ecological footprint (EF)(production)
	Generic	Ecological footprint (EF) (consumption)
	Maintaining nutrient cycles	(Nutrient circularity indicator) Need further development
Recirculate	Recycle	Circular material use rate (CMU)
	Recycle	Recycling rates (R) %
	Recycle	Percent designed recyclability rate of outflow
	Recycle	Average recycled content of inflow
	Recycle	Percent actual recycled material from outflow
	Reuse	Average reuse content of an inflow
	Reuse	Percent actual reused product and component derived from outflow
	Reuse	Percent designed recyclability rate of outflow
	Durability	Average lifetime of product or material relative to industry average
	Recirculate	Percent actual recirculation of out flow for the biological cycle

Extend the high-quality use including cascading	No indicator recommended
Positive effect on economic viability	Material productivity Resource intensity index
Positive effect on social equality	No indicator recommended
Complex indicator	No indicator recommended

5.3 Indicator-set for the wood sector

A separate indicator set was developed for the wood sector, as 59 wood-specific indicators were identified at the meso level (50 indicators) and macro level (9 indicators). No indicators were identified at the micro level, and consequently, it was not possible to develop an indicator set for this level. Furthermore, as only 9 indicators were identified at the macro level, a choice was made to create only one indicator set covering both the meso and macro levels. The indicators set can be used to assess the circularity of the wood sector for regions and countries. However, the scoring of the indicators was relatively low, between 1 and -8. This indicates a low maturity level of the indicators and/or difficulties in harmonising with LCA. This should be kept in mind when applying the indicator set.

5.3.1 Reduce reliance on fossil resources

Three indicators were identified covering the circularity strategy to reduce reliance on fossil resources at the meso level: fossil fuel consumption by use, volume of thinned timber and the amount that can be used as wood biomass, and the electricity/thermal efficiency of woody biomass and creation of economic value. At the macro level, two indicators were identified: I_5 , which is the ratio between the CO₂ emissions saved by the timber sold for energy production and the total cubic meters collected, and I_6 , which is the ratio between deadwood used for energy production and total deadwood. I_5 had the highest score (0) and is therefore selected for the indicator set. Furthermore, insufficient documentation was provided for two of the indicators at the meso level, and it was therefore difficult to proceed with these. I_5 only covers energy, and no indicators were identified for the sub-strategy of renewability. Consequently, the generic indicators can be applied here.

5.3.2 Use resources efficiently, including residues and waste

For the circularity strategy use resources efficiently, including residues and waste, no indicators were identified at the meso level, and only two indicators were identified at the macro level. The indicator with the highest score was I_1 , which covers the ratio (on an annual basis) between the economic value of the wood harvested per cubic meter and the forest area. This indicator covers only efficient use of resources (based on economic value). However, no indicators were identified covering the waste aspect; consequently, the generic indicators can be used as a supplement here.

5.3.3 Ensure regeneration of natural systems

Several indicators were identified covering the circularity strategy ensure regeneration of natural systems at both the meso level (10 indicators) and macro level (3 indicators). Indicators were identified for three CE sub-strategies: generic indicators and indicators targeting sustainable sources and maintaining carbon cycles. No indicators were identified for maintaining nutrient cycles; it is therefore necessary to supplement with the generic indicators here. The generic indicator with the highest score was land use change (1), and consequently, this is included in the indicator set. For sustainable sourcing, the indicators covering the amount of timber harvested/amount of replanting and the amount of certified forest biomass and residues had the highest score (-4), and they are therefore included. For the sub-strategy to maintain carbon cycles, two

Table 29: Overview of the selected indicators on macro level

indicators were identified: carbon stock and CO₂ absorption. Both scored (-4) and are consequently included in the indicator-set.

5.3.4 Recirculate

For the circularity strategy recirculate, only two indicators were identified, and both covered the macro level namely, recycle (I₄), covering the economic differential (%) gain from a more rational valorisation of the valuable wood assortments, and reuse (I₃), covering the product lifespan before it is used for energy generation (in years). The two indicators cover different sub-strategies within recirculate. Recycle (I₄), despite its name, covers the strategy more generically as it targets all more rational valorisations, whereas I₃ covers durability as it targets the extended lifespan of a product due to reuse and recycling strategies. Despite their relatively low scores (-2 and -3), both indicators are included in the indicator set.

5.3.5 Extend the high-quality use, including cascading

Seven indicators were identified targeting the circularity strategy "extend the high-quality use, including cascading." All indicators were from Costa et al. (2023)(2023) and had a very specific focus on circular economy in an Alpine collective ownership. Consequently, it can be a bit hard to make some of the indicators applicable to the wood sector more generically, and the indicators also had low scores (from -5 to -6). The indicator with the highest score was the percentage/volume of wastes and residues that become new resources, and consequently, the indicator was included in the indicator set. In the article, the indicator is defined as a cascading indicator; however, it could also be argued that it is more related to the recirculate strategies in the framework applied in this project. Nevertheless, it was selected to follow the categorisation in the original source.

5.3.6 Positive effect on social equality

A vast number of indicators (28) were identified covering the circularity strategy "positive effect on social equality," all covering the meso level. However, all but one are from Costa et al. (2023)(2023) and have a low score between -6 and -7. So again, many of the indicators have a very specific focus on Alpine collective ownerships and cannot be directly applied in another setting. The indicator with the highest score was the number of jobs created by forestry employees (-2), and it originates from another reference. Consequently, this indicator was selected for the indicator set.

5.3.7 Complex indicators

No indicators were identified for the wood sector.

CE Strategy	CE-Substrategy	Indicator
Reduce reliance on fossil resources	Renewability	No indicator identified
	Energy	Ratio between the CO ₂ emissions saved by the timber sold for energy production and the total cubic meter collected
Use resources efficiency including residues and waste	Resource efficiency	Ratio (on an annual basis) between the economic value of the wood harvested per cubic meter and the forest area (reduced)
	Waste	No indicators identified
Ensure regeneration of natural systems	Generic	Land use change
	Sustainable sourcing	Amount of timber harvested/ amount of replanting
	Sustainable sourcing	Amount of certified forest biomass and residues
	Maintaining nutrient cycles	No one identified
	Maintaining carbon cycles	Carbon stock and CO ₂ absorption
Recirculate	Generic	Recycle I ₄ : The economic differential (%) gain from a more rational valorization of the valuable wood assortments
	Durability (due to reuse and recycling)	Reuse I ₃ : Product life span before it is used for energy generation (years)
Extend the high-quality use including cascading		Percentage/ volume of wastes and residues that become new resources
Positive effect on economic viability		Creation of economic value based on the production of electricity/ thermal efficiency of woody biomass
Positive effect on social equality		Number of jobs created by forestry employees
Complex indicator		No indicators identified

Table 30: Overview of the indicator set for wood sector on meso and macro level

5.4 Guidance Document for Sustainability Assessment of circular bio-based strategies

The guidance document is based on the understanding provided by Vural et al. (2022) regarding how to assess the sustainability of BbS and their nine evaluation principles, which should be considered when assessing the circularity of BbS. For simplification, these have been reduced to seven principles and one category called "complex indicators," which covers more than one strategy. Circularity indicators for BbS were then identified in the scientific literature and categorized according to the evaluation principles (Chapter 5). Subsequently, the indicators were scored, and based on the scoring, indicators were selected for the different evaluation principles (Chapter 6). However, as not all indicators are equally developed and mature, it was not possible to provide indicators for all strategies, and it was also necessary to supplement with indicators from the ISO 59020 standard. The process of making a sustainability assessment targeting circularity.

5.4.1 The procedure for making the sustainability assessment of circular BbS

As the final step a guidance for the sustainability assessment targeting circularity is developed building on the previous work and inspired by the procedure in the ISO 59020 standard. The procedure is as follows:

Step 1: Define the goal and scope of the sustainability assessment targeting circularity

- Define the objective of the sustainability assessment targeting circularity
- Define the system level (micro, macro, or wood sector)

Step 2: Define the sector under consideration for the sustainability assessment

- Describe the sector to be assessed

Step 3: Select specific CE strategies and sub-strategies relevant for the BbS under consideration

- Consider which circularity strategies are relevant for the specific sector
- Consider whether it is necessary to assess sub-strategies
- The strategies and sub-strategies are:
 - o Reduce reliance on fossil resources (energy efficiency and renewability)
 - o Use resources efficiently, including use of residues and wastes (resource efficiency and waste reduction)
 - o Regenerate (generic, sustainable sourcing, avoid hazardous substances, maintain nutrient cycles, and maintain carbon cycles)
 - o Extend the high-quality use, including cascading
 - o Positive effect on economic viability
 - o Positive effect on social viability
 - o Complex indicators covering more than one circular economy strategy

Step 4: Select the relevant indicators in accordance with the CE strategies and potentially sub-strategies

- Based on the identified strategies and sub-strategies, create the indicator set relevant for your sustainability assessment targeting circularity based on the indicator sets in Table 28, 29, and 30)

Step 5: Identify data needs

- Specify the data needed
- Consider the required data quality (primary data and secondary data)

Step 6: Acquire data

- Acquire the necessary data from internal and/or external sources
- Assess the consequences of missing or inaccurate data

Step 7: Perform the calculations and check results

- Ensure that the data is balanced and normalized
- Check calculations and results

Step 8: Communicate the results

- Present the results and data limitations

6 CONCLUSION

This deliverable has addressed the challenge of assessing circularity in bio-based systems (BbS) by developing a structured framework of indicators tailored to the characteristics and sustainability strategies of the circular bioeconomy. A tailored framework of circularity strategies and sub-strategies was identified and adopted to the specific project covering the following strategies: reduce reliance on fossil resources and increase share of renewable resources, use resource efficiently including residues, regenerate, recirculate, extend the high quality use of biomass (including cascading) positive effect on economic viability and positive effect on social viability. Through a systematic and critical review of existing scientific literature, international standards (notably the ISO 59000 series), and relevant EU projects (CALIMERO and ORIENTING), the study identified 143 unique circularity indicators and categorized them across eight core strategies relevant to BbS: reducing fossil reliance, resource efficiency (including residues and waste), regeneration of natural systems, recirculation, cascading/high-quality use, impacts on economic viability and social equity and complex indicators.

The key outcome of the work is the development of three indicator sets:

Micro-level generic indicator set: This set targets assessments at the level of individual products, processes, or organizations. The selected indicators prioritize simplicity, data accessibility, and clarity of interpretation, making them suitable for practical application in industrial or small-scale bio-based solutions. They cover resource and energy intensity, waste generation, recycling efficiency, and product longevity. Notably, indicators such as the Material Circularity Indicator (MCI), Feedstock and Waste Factors, and Product Renewability offer quantifiable measures that can be aligned with life cycle assessment (LCA) data.

Macro-level generic indicator set: Designed for policy-level or territorial analyses, this set draws heavily on indicators already used in Eurostat and national statistical databases. It includes high-level metrics such as resource productivity (GDP per unit of material use), circular material use rate, ecological footprint, land use change, and nutrient circularity at the regional scale. These indicators facilitate cross-country or sectoral comparison and enable monitoring of system-wide progress toward circularity.

Wood-sector-specific indicator set: Given the relative abundance of sector-specific indicators in the literature for the forest and wood value chains, a dedicated set was developed for this sector. These indicators reflect the particularities of biomass cascading, sustainable forest management, and long-term carbon storage. Examples include biogenic carbon stock in harvested wood products, cascading use intensity, and forest regeneration balance. Indicators also address social dimensions, such as local employment and cooperative ownership practices in forest-based systems.

Each set was derived through a transparent scoring and selection process based on twelve evaluation criteria, documented in annexed Excel matrices (Appendices 2 and 3). The process included expert validation and iterative discussion among project partners. In total, over 50 indicators were selected, covering the full range of CE strategies across levels and offering flexibility for case-specific adaptation.

The deliverable concludes with a practical guidance document that provides instructions on how to apply the indicator sets, including categorization, system boundary considerations, and integration with life cycle assessment (LCA). Together, the results represent a significant step toward harmonizing circularity assessment in the bioeconomy and supporting evidence-based sustainability evaluations of circular bio-based strategies in research and practice.

7 REFERENCES

- Adibi, N., Lafhaj, Z., Yehya, M., Payet, J., 2017. Global Resource Indicator for life cycle impact assessment: Applied in wind turbine case study. *J Clean Prod* 165, 1517–1528. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.07.226>
- Aksnes, D.W., Sivertsen, G., 2019. A Criteria-based Assessment of the Coverage of Scopus and Web of Science. *Journal of Data and Information Science* 4, 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.2478/jdis-2019-0001>
- Ardente, F., Mathieux, F., 2014. Identification and assessment of product's measures to improve resource efficiency: the case-study of an Energy using Product. *J Clean Prod* 83, 126–141. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2014.07.058>
- Azevedo, S., Godina, R., Matias, J., 2017. Proposal of a Sustainable Circular Index for Manufacturing Companies. *Resources* 6, 63. <https://doi.org/10.3390/resources6040063>
- Bachmann, T.M., Hackenhaar, I.C., Horn, R., Charter, M., Gehring, F., Graf, R., Huysveld, S., Alvarenga, R.A.F., 2021. ORIENTING D1.4: Critical evaluation of material criticality and product-related circularity approaches.
- Blomsma, F., Pieroni, M., Kravchenko, M., Pigosso, D.C.A., Hildenbrand, J., Kristinsdottir, A.R., Kristoffersen, E., Shahbazi, S., Nielsen, K.D., Jönbrink, A.-K., Li, J., Wiik, C., McAlloone, T.C., 2019. Developing a circular strategies framework for manufacturing companies to support circular economy-oriented innovation. *J Clean Prod* 241, 118271. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.118271>
- Bocken, N.M.P., de Pauw, I., Bakker, C., van der Grinten, B., 2016. Product design and business model strategies for a circular economy. *Journal of Industrial and Production Engineering* 33, 308–320. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21681015.2016.1172124>
- Borucke, M., Moore, D., Cranston, G., Gracey, K., Iha, K., Larson, J., Lazarus, E., Morales, J.C., Wackernagel, M., Galli, A., 2013. Accounting for demand and supply of the biosphere's regenerative capacity: The National Footprint Accounts' underlying methodology and framework. *Ecol Indic* 24, 518–533. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2012.08.005>
- Brunner, P.H., Rechberger, H., 2017. *Handbook of material flow analysis: For Environmental, Resource, and Waste Engineers*, Second Edition. ed. CRC Press: Taylor & Francis Group, New York.
- Cayzer, S., Griffiths, P., Beghetto, V., 2017. Design of indicators for measuring product performance in the circular economy. *International Journal of Sustainable Engineering* 10, 289–298. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19397038.2017.1333543>
- Cobo, S., Dominguez-Ramos, A., Irabien, A., 2018. Trade-Offs between Nutrient Circularity and Environmental Impacts in the Management of Organic Waste. *Environ Sci Technol* 52, 10923–10933. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.8b01590>
- Corona, B., Hoefnagels, R., Vural Gürsel, I., Moretti, C., van Veen, M., Junginger, M., 2022. Metrics for minimising environmental impacts while maximising circularity in biobased products: The case of lignin-based asphalt. *J Clean Prod* 379. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.134829>
- Costa, E., Kratzer, A., Pesci, C., Burgia, I., 2023. Accounting for a forest-based circular economy in an Alpine collective ownership. *Accounting Forum* 47, 583–613. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01559982.2023.2214703>
- da Costa, L.F., de Medeiros Melo Neto, O., de Macêdo, A.L.F., de Figueiredo Lopes Lucena, L.C., de Figueiredo Lopes Lucena, L., 2024. Optimizing recycled asphalt mixtures with zeolite, cottonseed oil, and varied RAP content for enhanced performance and circular economy impact. *Case Studies in Construction Materials* 20, e02707. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cscm.2023.e02707>

- Delahaye, R., Tunn, V.S.C., Tukker, A., 2023. Developing a material flow monitor for the Netherlands from national statistical data. *J Ind Ecol* 27, 408–422. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.13365>
- Deus, R.M., Bezerra, B.S., Battistelle, R.A.G., 2019. Solid waste indicators and their implications for management practice. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology* 16, 1129–1144. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13762-018-2163-3>
- Di Maio, F., Rem, P.C., Baldé, K., Polder, M., 2017. Measuring resource efficiency and circular economy: A market value approach. *Resour Conserv Recycl* 122, 163–171. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2017.02.009>
- Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2015. Growth within: a circular economy vision for a competitive europe. Ellen MacArthur Foundation 100. <https://doi.org/Article>
- Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2013. Towards the Circular Economy 1: Economic and business rationale for an accelerated transition. <https://doi.org/10.1162/108819806775545321>
- Escribà-Gelonch, M., Butler, G.D., Goswami, A., Tran, N.N., Hessel, V., 2023. Definition of agronomic circular economy metrics and use for assessment for a nanofertilizer case study. *Plant Physiology and Biochemistry* 196, 917–924. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.plaphy.2023.02.042>
- European Environmental Agency, 2024. Management of used and waste textiles in Europe's circular economy [WWW Document]. Briefing.
- Fernández Ocamica, V., Bernardes Figueirêdo, M., Zapata, S., Bartolomé, C., 2024. Assessment of EU Bio-Based Economy Sectors Based on Environmental, Socioeconomic, and Technical Indicators. *Sustainability* 16, 1971. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16051971>
- Franklin-Johnson, E., Figge, F., Canning, L., 2016. Resource duration as a managerial indicator for Circular Economy performance. *J Clean Prod* 133, 589–598. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.05.023>
- Gallo, F., Manzardo, A., Camana, D., Fedele, A., Scipioni, A., 2024. Integration of a circular economy metric with life cycle assessment: methodological proposal of compared agri-food products. *Int J Life Cycle Assess* 29, 1359–1379. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-022-02130-0>
- Gao, Chengkang, Gao, Chengbo, Song, K., Fang, K., 2020. Pathways towards regional circular economy evaluated using material flow analysis and system dynamics. *Resour Conserv Recycl* 154, 104527. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2019.104527>
- Garcia-Herrero, I., Margallo, M., Laso, J., Battle-Bayer, L., Bala, A., Fullana-i-Palmer, P., Vazquez-Rowe, I., Gonzalez, M.J., Amo-Setien, F., Durá, M.J., Sarabia, C., Abajas, R., Quiñones, A., Irabien, A., Aldaco, R., 2019. Nutritional data management of food losses and waste under a life cycle approach: Case study of the Spanish agri-food system. *Journal of Food Composition and Analysis* 82, 103223. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfca.2019.05.006>
- Godiin, J., Marshall, K., Pereira, A., Tuppen, C., Harrmann, S., Jones, S., Krieger, T., Lenges, C., Coleman, B., Pierce, C.J., n.d. Circularity Indicators: An Approach to Measuring Circularity, Methodology.
- Gómez-Sagasti, M.T., Hernández, A., Artetxe, U., Garbisu, C., Becerril, J.M., 2018. How Valuable Are Organic Amendments as Tools for the Phytomanagement of Degraded Soils? The Knowns, Known Unknowns, and Unknowns. *Front Sustain Food Syst* 2. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2018.00068>
- Guevara-Rivera, E., Osorno-Hinojosa, R., Zaldivar-Carrillo, V., Perez-Ortiz, H., 2021. Dynamic simulation methodology for implementing circular economy: A new case study. *Journal of Industrial Engineering and Management* 14, 850. <https://doi.org/10.3926/jiem.3609>

- Haupt, M., Vadenbo, C., Hellweg, S., 2017. Do We Have the Right Performance Indicators for the Circular Economy?: Insight into the Swiss Waste Management System. *J Ind Ecol* 21, 615–627. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.12506>
- Hildebrandt, J., Bezama, A., Thrän, D., 2017. Cascade use indicators for selected biopolymers: Are we aiming for the right solutions in the design for recycling of bio-based polymers? *Waste Management & Research: The Journal for a Sustainable Circular Economy* 35, 367–378. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0734242X16683445>
- Hoehn, D., Margallo, M., Laso, J., García-Herrero, I., Bala, A., Fullana-i-Palmer, P., Irabien, A., Aldaco, R., 2019. Energy Embedded in Food Loss Management and in the Production of Uneaten Food: Seeking a Sustainable Pathway. *Energies (Basel)* 12, 767. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en12040767>
- Horvath, B., Bahna, M., Fogarassy, C., 2019. The ecological criteria of circular growth and the rebound risk of closed loops. *Sustainability (Switzerland)* 11. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11102961>
- Huysman, S., De Schaepmeester, J., Ragaert, K., Dewulf, J., De Meester, S., 2017. Performance indicators for a circular economy: A case study on post-industrial plastic waste. *Resour Conserv Recycl* 120, 46–54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2017.01.013>
- Huysman, S., Debaveye, S., Schaubroeck, T., Meester, S. De, Ardente, F., Mathieux, F., Dewulf, J., 2015. The recyclability benefit rate of closed-loop and open-loop systems: A case study on plastic recycling in Flanders. *Resour Conserv Recycl* 101, 53–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2015.05.014>
- ISO, 2024a. ISO 59010: Circular economy - Guidance on the transition of business models and value networks.
- ISO, 2024b. ISO 59004: Circular economy - Vocabulary, principles and guidance for implementation.
- ISO, 2024c. ISO 59014: Environmental Management and circular economy . International Standardisation Organisation.
- ISO, 2024d. ISO 59020: Circular Economy - Measuring and Assessing circularity performance. International Standard Organisation.
- ISO, 2024e. ISO 59040: Circular economy - Product circularity data sheet. International Standardisation Organisation.
- Karayılan, S., Yılmaz, Ö., Uysal, Ç., Naneci, S., 2021. Prospective evaluation of circular economy practices within plastic packaging value chain through optimization of life cycle impacts and circularity. *Resour Conserv Recycl* 173, 105691. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.105691>
- Kayal, B., Abu-Ghunmi, D., Abu-Ghunmi, L., Archenti, A., Nicolescu, M., Larkin, C., Corbet, S., 2019. An economic index for measuring firm's circularity: The case of water industry. *J Behav Exp Finance* 21, 123–129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbef.2018.11.007>
- Kooduvalli, K., Sharma, B., Webb, E., Vaidya, U., Ozcan, S., 2019. Sustainability Indicators for Biobased Product Manufacturing: A Systematic Review. *J Sustain Dev* 12, 55. <https://doi.org/10.5539/jsd.v12n1p55>
- Kowalski, Z., Kulczycka, J., Makara, A., Verhé, R., De Clercq, G., 2022. Assessment of Energy Recovery from Municipal Waste Management Systems Using Circular Economy Quality Indicators. *Energies (Basel)* 15, 8625. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15228625>
- Kusumo, F., Mahlia, T.M.I., Pradhan, S., Ong, H.C., Silitonga, A.S., Fattah, I.M.R., Nghiem, L.D., Mofijur, M., 2022. A framework to assess indicators of the circular economy in biological systems. *Environ Technol Innov* 28, 102945. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eti.2022.102945>

- Laner, D., Zoboli, O., Rechberger, H., 2017. Statistical entropy analysis to evaluate resource efficiency: Phosphorus use in Austria. *Ecol Indic* 83, 232–242. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2017.07.060>
- Li, Y., Matsumoto, T., Fujiyama, A., 2021. Consideration and Application of Evaluation Indicators of Regional Circular and Ecological Sphere (CES) for the Utilization of Woody Biomass. *Nature Environment and Pollution Technology* 20. <https://doi.org/10.46488/NEPT.2021.V20I05.015>
- Lim, C.H., Chuen, W.W.Z., Foo, J.Q., Tan, T.J., How, B.S., Ng, W.P.Q., Lam, H.L., 2019. Circular sustainability optimisation model for diverse oil crops feedstock system via element targeting approach. *Chem Eng Trans* 76. <https://doi.org/10.3303/CET1976186>
- Linder, M., Sarasini, S., van Loon, P., 2017. A Metric for Quantifying Product-Level Circularity. *J Ind Ecol* 21, 545–558. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.12552>
- Lokesh, K., Matharu, A.S., Kookos, I.K., Ladakis, D., Koutinas, A., Morone, P., Clark, J., 2020. Hybridised sustainability metrics for use in life cycle assessment of bio-based products: resource efficiency and circularity. *Green Chemistry* 22, 803–813. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9GC02992C>
- Luthin, A., Traverso, M., Crawford, R.H., 2024. Circular life cycle sustainability assessment: An integrated framework. *J Ind Ecol* 28, 41–58. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.13446>
- Macias Aragonés, M., Arroyo Torralvo, F., 2024. How to select the best approach for circular economy assessment? 3D positioning framework, decision support tool and critical analysis for bio-based systems. *Environ Impact Assess Rev* 106, 107493. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2024.107493>
- Mantalovas, K., Di Mino, G., 2020. Integrating Circularity in the Sustainability Assessment of Asphalt Mixtures. *Sustainability* 12, 594. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12020594>
- Mesa, J.A., Sierra-Fontalvo, L., Ortegon, K., Gonzalez-Quiroga, A., 2024. Advancing circular bioeconomy: A critical review and assessment of indicators. *Sustain Prod Consum* 46, 324–342. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2024.03.006>
- Molina-Sánchez, E., Leyva-Díaz, J.C., Cortés-García, F.J., Molina-Moreno, V., 2018. Proposal of Sustainability Indicators for the Waste Management from the Paper Industry within the Circular Economy Model. *Water (Basel)* 10, 1014. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w10081014>
- Moraga, G., Huysveld, S., De Meester, S., Dewulf, J., 2021. Development of circularity indicators based on the in-use occupation of materials. *J Clean Prod* 279, 123889. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.123889>
- Navare, K., Muys, B., Vrancken, K.C., Van Acker, K., 2021. Circular economy monitoring – How to make it apt for biological cycles? *Resour Conserv Recycl* 170, 105563. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.105563>
- OECD, 2017. OECD Green Growth Studies: Green Growth Indicators 2017.
- ORIENTING, 2024. ORIENTING: About us. [WWW Document].
- Page, M.J., McKenzie, J.E., Bossuyt, P.M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T.C., Mulrow, C.D., Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J.M., Akl, E.A., Brennan, S.E., Chou, R., Glanville, J., Grimshaw, J.M., Hróbjartsson, A., Lalu, M.M., Li, T., Loder, E.W., Mayo-Wilson, E., McDonald, S., McGuinness, L.A., Stewart, L.A., Thomas, J., Tricco, A.C., Welch, V.A., Whiting, P., Moher, D., 2021. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* n71. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n71>
- Papamichael, I., Pappas, G., Siegel, J.E., Zorpas, A.A., 2022. Unified waste metrics: A gamified tool in next-generation strategic planning. *Science of The Total Environment* 833, 154835. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.154835>

- Pauliuk, S., 2018. Critical appraisal of the circular economy standard BS 8001:2017 and a dashboard of quantitative system indicators for its implementation in organizations. *Resour Conserv Recycl* 129, 81–92. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2017.10.019>
- Perez-Mercado, L.F., Perez-Mercado, C.A., Vinnerås, B., Simha, P., 2022. Nutrient stocks, flows and balances for the Bolivian agri-food system: Can recycling human excreta close the nutrient circularity gap? *Front Environ Sci* 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2022.956325>
- Pieratti, E., Paletto, A., De Meo, I., Fagarazzi, C., Rillo Migliorini, M.G., 2019. Assessing the forest-wood chain at local level: A Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) based on the circular bioeconomy principles. *Ann For Res* 62. <https://doi.org/10.15287/afr.2018.1238>
- Poponi, S., Arcese, G., Pacchera, F., Martucci, O., 2022. Evaluating the transition to the circular economy in the agri-food sector: Selection of indicators. *Resour Conserv Recycl* 176, 105916. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.105916>
- Poponi, S., Ruggieri, A., Pacchera, F., Arcese, G., 2024. The circular potential of a Bio-District: indicators for waste management. *British Food Journal* 126, 290–308. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BFJ-12-2022-1137>
- Potting, J., Hekkert, M., Worrell, E., Hanemaaijer, A., 2017. Circular Economy: Measuring innovation in the product chain - Policy report. PBL Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency PBL publication number 2544.
- Qing, Y., Qiongqiong, G., Mingyue, C., 2011. Study and Integrative Evaluation on the development of Circular Economy of Shaanxi Province. *Energy Procedia* 5, 1568–1578. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2011.03.268>
- Razza, F., Briani, C., Breton, T., Marazza, D., 2020. Metrics for quantifying the circularity of bioplastics: The case of bio-based and biodegradable mulch films. *Resour Conserv Recycl* 159, 104753. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2020.104753>
- Reike, D., Vermeulen, W.J.V., Witjes, S., 2018. The circular economy: New or Refurbished as CE 3.0? — Exploring Controversies in the Conceptualization of the Circular Economy through a Focus on History and Resource Value Retention Options. *Resour Conserv Recycl* 135, 246–264. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2017.08.027>
- Reuter, M., Van Schaik, A., 2016. Strategic metal recycling: adaptive metallurgical processing infrastructure and technology are essential for a Circular Economy. *Responsabilité & Environment*.
- Reuter, M.A., van Schaik, A., Gediga, J., 2015. Simulation-based design for resource efficiency of metal production and recycling systems: Cases - copper production and recycling, e-waste (LED lamps) and nickel pig iron. *Int J Life Cycle Assess* 20, 671–693. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-015-0860-4>
- Rocchi, L., Paolotti, L., Cortina, C., Fagioli, F.F., Boggia, A., 2021. Measuring circularity: an application of modified Material Circularity Indicator to agricultural systems. *Agricultural and Food Economics* 9, 9. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40100-021-00182-8>
- Schaubroeck, T., Ding, T., Rydberg, T., Midander, K., Johansson, H., Sircar, T., Vrasdonk, E., Charpentier Poncelet, A., Schrijvers, D., Vidinha, M., Barbero, E.E., Carrizosa, A.B., Judalet, Q., Fernández, M.G., Escobar, R.M., Amaral, M., 2024. CALIMERO: Characterization of the main methodological gaps in sustainability assessment of bio-based sectors.
- Scheepens, A.E., Vogtländer, J.G., Brezet, J.C., 2016. Two life cycle assessment (LCA) based methods to analyse and design complex (regional) circular economy systems. Case: making water tourism more sustainable. *J Clean Prod* 114, 257–268. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2015.05.075>

- Schrijvers, D., Vidinha, M., Adibi, N., Charpentier, A., Schaubroeck, T., Saidani, M., Rydberg, T., Barbero, E.E., Fernández, M.G., Oliveira, S.L., Amaral, M., 2024. CALIMERO: Improving Bio-based Industries Life Cycle Sustainability: D3.3. Circular economy and criticality assessment methodology definition.
- Sgarbossa, F., Russo, I., 2017. A proactive model in sustainable food supply chain: Insight from a case study. *Int J Prod Econ* 183, 596–606. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2016.07.022>
- Smol, M., Kulczycka, J., Avdiushchenko, A., 2017. Circular economy indicators in relation to eco-innovation in European regions. *Clean Technol Environ Policy* 19, 669–678. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10098-016-1323-8>
- Spierling, S., Venkatachalam, V., Behnsen, H., Herrmann, C., Endres, H.-J., 2019. Bioplastics and Circular Economy—Performance Indicators to Identify Optimal Pathways. pp. 147–154. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-92237-9_16
- Stanchev, P., Vasilaki, V., Egas, D., Colon, J., Ponsá, S., Katsou, E., 2020. Multilevel environmental assessment of the anaerobic treatment of dairy processing effluents in the context of circular economy. *J Clean Prod* 261, 121139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.121139>
- Stegmann, P., Gerritse, T., Shen, L., Londo, M., Puente, Á., Junginger, M., 2023. The global warming potential and the material utility of PET and bio-based PEF bottles over multiple recycling trips. *J Clean Prod* 395, 136426. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.136426>
- Stegmann, P., Londo, M., Junginger, M., 2020. The circular bioeconomy: Its elements and role in European bioeconomy clusters. *Resources, Conservation & Recycling: X* 6, 100029. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcrx.2019.100029>
- Stillitano, T., Falcone, G., Iofrida, N., Spada, E., Gulisano, G., De Luca, A.I., 2022. A customized multi-cycle model for measuring the sustainability of circular pathways in agri-food supply chains. *Science of The Total Environment* 844, 157229. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.157229>
- Suarez-Visbal, L.J., Rosales-Carreón, J., Corona, B., Alomoto, W., Worrell, E., 2024. Walking the circular talk: Analyzing the soft and hard aspects of circular economy implementation of ten business cases within the textile and apparel value chain. *J Clean Prod* 476, 143683. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2024.143683>
- Vamza, I., Kubule, A., Zihare, L., Valters, K., Blumberga, D., 2021. Bioresource utilization index – A way to quantify and compare resource efficiency in production. *J Clean Prod* 320, 128791. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.128791>
- van Veen, M., Moretti, C., Corona, B., Hoefnagels, R., Junginger, M., Vuran-Gürsel, Jongerius, A., Russel, S., Obydenkova, S., 2021. comparing the production, life cycle cost and environmental life cycle costs of bitumen-based asphalt with 2nd generation biorefinery lignin-based asphalt . *Collaboration in asPhalt Applications with Ilgning in the Netherlands (CHAPLIN)* 1-57.
- Vázquez-Rowe, I., Laso, J., Margallo, M., Garcia-Herrero, I., Hoehn, D., Amo-Setién, F., Bala, A., Abajas, R., Sarabia, C., Durá, M.J., Fullana-i-Palmer, P., Aldaco, R., 2020. Food loss and waste metrics: a proposed nutritional cost footprint linking linear programming and life cycle assessment. *Int J Life Cycle Assess* 25, 1197–1209. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-019-01655-1>
- Vogiantzi, C., Tserpes, K., 2023. On the Definition, Assessment, and Enhancement of Circular Economy across Various Industrial Sectors: A Literature Review and Recent Findings. *Sustainability* 15, 16532. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su152316532>
- Vural Gursel, I., Elbersen, B., Meesters, K.P.H., 2023. Monitoring circular biobased economy – Systematic review of circularity indicators at the micro level. *Resour Conserv Recycl* 197, 107104.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2023.107104>

Vural Gursel, I., Elbersen, B., Meesters, K.P.H., van Leeuwen, M., 2022. Defining Circular Economy Principles for Biobased Products. *Sustainability* 14, 12780. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141912780>

Vuta, Mariana, Vuta, Mihai, Enciu, A., Cioaca, S.-I., 2018. Assessment of the Circular Economy's Impact in the EU Economic Growth. *www.amfiteatrueconomic.ro* 20, 248. <https://doi.org/10.24818/EA/2018/48/248>

Wen, Z., Meng, X., 2015. Quantitative assessment of industrial symbiosis for the promotion of circular economy: a case study of the printed circuit boards industry in China's Suzhou New District. *J Clean Prod* 90, 211–219. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2014.03.041>

Wiedemann, S.G., Nguyen, Q. V., Clarke, S.J., 2022. Using LCA and Circularity Indicators to Measure the Sustainability of Textiles—Examples of Renewable and Non-Renewable Fibres. *Sustainability* 14, 16683. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142416683>

Woźniak, E., Tyczewska, A., Twardowski, T., 2021. Bioeconomy development factors in the European Union and Poland. *N Biotechnol* 60, 2–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nbt.2020.07.004>

Yilan, G., Cordella, M., Morone, P., 2023. Evaluating and managing the sustainability performance of investments in green and sustainable chemistry: Development and application of an approach to assess bio-based and biodegradable plastics. *Current Research in Green and Sustainable Chemistry* 6, 100353. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crgsc.2022.100353>

Zampori, L., Pant, R., 2019. Suggestions for updating the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) method.

Zorpas, A.A., 2024. The hidden concept and the beauty of multiple “R” in the framework of waste strategies development reflecting to circular economy principles. *Science of The Total Environment* 952, 175508. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.175508>